

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar, Mukka, Mangalore – 574 146, Phone :0824-2477456

(State Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013 empowered to award degrees under Section 22 of UGC Act of UGC, New Delhi, & Member of Association of Indian Universities, New Delhi)

Web :www.srinivasuniversity.ac.in, Email: info@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Program Syllabus

for

**Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) Programme Core (Based on
UGC –LOCF)**

The realities have changed, the context has changed, the practice is changing and therefore the approach of learning has to alongside change.

Board of Studies in Social Work

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

(2021 ONWARDS)

R.19 Semester wise Subjects details

I SEMESTER BSW SEMESTER I: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW01	Fundamentals of social work (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW02	Sociology for Social Workers (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW03 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Early Childhood Development	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW03 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Principles of Management									
4	21BSW04	Field Practicum – I (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW05	Fundamentals of Communication I (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW06 K	Kannada I (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BSW06 H	Hindi I (AECC)									
	21BSW06 M	Malayalam I (AECC)									
	21BSW06 O	Online Mode I (AECC)									
7	21BSW07	Digital Proficiency I (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW08	Health & Wellness (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW09	Basics of Nutrition (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BSW10	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
Total						300				750	28

*DSC- Discipline

*DSC- Discipline Elective

*OE -open Elective

*SEC – Skilled Enhancement Courses

AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

II SEMESTER BSW
SEMESTER II: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW11	Social Work Methods (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW12	Human Growth and Development (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW13 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Human Resource Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW13 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Youth Development through Social Work									
4	21BSW14	Field Practicum – II (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW15	Fundamentals of Communication II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW16 K	Kannada II (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BSW16 H	Hindi II (AECC)									
	21BSW16 M	Malayalam II (AECC)									
	21BSW16 O	Online Mode II (AECC)									
7	21BSW17	Digital Proficiency II (SEC)	-			20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW18	NSS (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW19	Life Skills (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BSW20	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
Total						320				750	28

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AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

III SEMESTER BSW
SEMESTER III: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW21	Rural, Urban and Tribal Community (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW22	Counseling and Guidance (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW23 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Disaster Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW23 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Management Information system									
4	21BSW24	Field Practicum – III (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW25	Functional English-I (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW26 K	Kannada III (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BSW26 H	Hindi III (AECC)									
	21BSW26 M	Malayalam III (AECC)									
	21BSW26 O	Online Mode III (AECC)									
7	21BSW27	Cyber Crime and Security (SEC)	-			20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW28	Games (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW29	Waste Management (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BSW30	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
		Total					320			750	28

*DSC- Discipline

*DSC- Discipline Elective

*OE -open Elective

*SEC – Skilled Enhancement Courses

AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER IV: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self-Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW31	Women And Development (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW32	NGO and Project Formulation (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW33 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Social Work Research	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW33 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) E- Business									
4	21BSW34	Field Practicum – IV (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW35	Functional English-II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW36 K	Kannada IV (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BSW36 H	Hindi IV (AECC)									
	21BSW36 M	Malayalam IV (AECC)									
	21BSW36 O	Online Mode IV (AECC)									
7	21BSW37	Entrepreneurship Start up (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW38	Yoga (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW39	Indian Constitution (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BSW40	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
Total						320				750	28

*DSC- Discipline

*DSC- Discipline Elective

*OE -open Elective

*SEC – Skilled Enhancement Courses

AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER V: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Internal			External	Total		
1	21BSW41	Citizen Participation and Local Self Governance (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4	
2	21BSW42	Sociology and Health (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4	
3	21BSW43 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Health care	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4	
	21BSW43 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Entrepreneur ship Development										
4	21BSW44	Field Practicum – V (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4	
5	21BSW45	Public Relationship (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3	
6	21BSW46	Excel and SPSS	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3	
7	21BSW47	Case Study on NGO (SEC)	-			20	-	50	-	50	2	
8	21BSW48	Music/Dance (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2	
9	21BSW49	Street Play (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2	
Total						300				750	28	

*DSC- Discipline

*DSC- Discipline Elective

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AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER VI: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW51	Internship & Dissertation to produce a News Magazine & Viva-Voce (SEC)	-	8	320	320	-	Internal Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300	External Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300 Viva-Voce exam = 150	750	28

SEMESTER VII: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) Honors

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW61	Social Case work (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW62	Social Group work (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW63	Organizational Psychology (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
4	21BSW64	NGO Case Study 1				200 HRS		350	100	450	16

SEMESTER VIII: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) Honors

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW71	Community Organization (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW72	Social Action and Social Welfare Administration (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW73	Gerontological Social Work (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
4	21BSW74	NGO Case Study 2				200 HRS		350	100	450	16

20. Examination Pattern:

Theory Papers: **Internal Assessment Marks**

Outline for continuous assessment activities for C1 and C2 are as follows:

Activities	C1	C2	Total Marks
Session Test		20	20
Seminars/Presentations/Activity	10		10
Case study /Assignment / Project work etc.		10	15
Attendance		5	5
Total	20 marks	30 marks	50 Marks

At the end of each semester, examinations will be conducted for all the papers to be covered in that semester and evaluation will be done for 50 marks each. The timings of the examination will be followed as per academic calendar.

21 Pattern of Question Paper in End Semester Examination:

The question paper pattern in each Semester Exam for 50 marks consists of Objective type questions 6 questions all to answer (6 marks), Very short answer three questions out of four questions (6 marks) Seven marks questions 4 out of 5 questions (28 marks) , and one long essay of 10 marks out of two (10 marks).

No. of	Type	Question/Marks	Total Marks
6 out of 6	Objective type	6 x 1 = 06	06
3 out of 4	Very short	3 x 2= 06	06
4 out of 5	Short essay	4 x 7 = 28	28
1 out of 2	Long essay	1 x 10 =10	10
Total Semester Marks			50

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 1

21BSW01- Fundamentals of Social Work

Subject Code	21BSW01	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To understand history and evolution of social work profession, both in India and the West
2. To develop insights into the origin and development of ideologies and approaches to social change
3. To Adapt Skills to understand contemporary reality in its historical context

Course Outcomes

CO1. Able to interpret social work as a profession

CO2. To Apply the various ideologies of social work

CO3. Defend awareness of values and ethics of the social work profession.

Content of Course

Hrs

MODULE –I

8 HRS

An Introduction to Social Work

Social Work: Concept, Meaning, Definitions, Objectives, Goals and Functions.

Introduction to the methods of Social Work.

Social Work its Relationship to other discipline; Sociology, Psychology, History, Public administration, law and Economics.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE –II

8 HRS

Historical Development of Social Work

Historical development of Social Work in America (USA)

Historical development of Social Work in Europe (UK)Elizabethan Poor Law 1601

Historical development of Social Work in India

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE –III

8 HRS

Social Work Profession in India

Emergence of Social Work Profession in India

Profession: Meaning, Definitions and Attributes

Social Work Profession: Issues and Challenges

Professional v/s Voluntary Approaches to Social Work

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

8 HRS

MODULE –IV

Principles, Values and Ethics of Social Work

Principles of Social Work

Values and Code of Ethics (NASW) of Social Work

Values of Social work: Relating to individual, problem, relationship, agency, practice

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE –V

8 HRS

Fields of Social Work

Community Development, Correctional Settings, Medical and Psychiatric Social Work, Family, Women and Child centered Social Work, Industrial Social Work, and Social Work with Marginalized Sections of the Society.

Role of NGO's and GO's

Pedagogy: PPT, Group Discussion, Video clips, Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

References:

Annie Pullen-Sansfaçon (2013), The Ethical Foundations of Social Work, Stephen Cowden Routledge,

Banks, S. (1995). Ethics and Values in Social Work: Practical Social Work Series, London: Macmillan Press Ltd.

Compton, B. R. (1980). Introduction to Social Welfare and Social Work. Illinois: The Dorsey Press.

Desai, Murli, (2006). Ideologies and Social Work: Historical and Contemporary Analyses, Rawat Publication, New Delhi

Friedlander, Walter A. (1977) Concepts and Methods of Social Work, New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd

Heun, Linda R., Heun, Richard E. (2001) Developing Skills for Human Interaction, London:

Charles E. Merrill Co.

Jacob, K. K. (Ed.) (1994) *Social Work Education in India—Retrospect and Prospect* Udaipur, Himansu Publications.

Joseph, Sherry (Ed.) (2000) *Social Work: In the Third Millennium (Some Concerns and Challenges)*, Sriniketan, Department of Social Work, Visva-Bharati.

National Association of Social Workers (2008) .*Code of Ethics of the National Association of Social Workers*. Washington, D.C.: NASW Press.

O' Hagan, Kieran, Kingsley, Jessica (2003) *Competence in Social Work Practice-A Practical Guide for Professionals*, London

Reamer & Fredric (2005) *Social Work Values and Ethics*, New Delhi: Rawat Publication Singh, D.K. and Bhartiya, A.K. (2010). *Social Work: Concept and Methods*. Lucknow: New Royal Book Company.

Skidmore, Rex A. (1982), *Introduction to Social Work*, New Jersey, Thackeray, Milton G. Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs.

Surendra Singh (Chief Editor) .(2012): *Encyclopedia of Social Work in India*. Lucknow: New Royal Book Company.

Journals

The Indian Journal of Social Work, Bi-annual, TISS, Mumbai (Maharashtra)

Perspectives in Social Work, College of Social Work, Nirmala Niketan, Mumbai (Maharashtra)

Social Work Journal, Bi-annual, Department of Social Work, Assam University, Silchar

Digital References

USC Suzanne Dworak-Peck School of Social Work (2014), *Introduction to Social Work*: Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jXRB1V5eVw&t=5s>

UH Class OET (2016) *Introduction to Social Work*, University of Houston: Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LtaCmORiP9A>

The Audiopedia (2017), *what is SOCIAL WORK? What does SOCIAL WORK mean? SOCIALWORK meaning, definition and explanation*: Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xj5-Vdh1B3E>

USC Suzanne Dworak-Peck School of Social Work (2017), *Legacies of Social Change. 100 years of Professional Social Work in the MODULE ed States*: Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a4VzRSnksmA>

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 1

21BSW02 Sociology for Social Workers

Subject Code	21BSW02	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To educate sociological interventions to enable learners as social workers
2. To disseminate knowledge on Social Interaction and culture.
3. To enable sociological thinking to improve interplay with society.
4. To educate on Social Process, changes, social inequality and social problems affecting human life.

Course Outcome

CO1. Compare to learn ~~fundamentals~~ of sociology.

CO2. Develop social interaction based on social institutions, social learning, culture

CO3. Defend quest for reaching out to social needs with requisite critical thinking to serve better.

Course content

MODULE – I

8 HRS

Introduction: Sociology- Definition

Nature and Scope, Contribution from Sociologists; Society-Definition, features, Types; Community; Social Institution- definition, features, Types- Family, Marriage, Religion, Education, Significance of Social Institutions.

Social learning- Conditioning, Identity taking, modelling, problem solving;

Pedagogy: Chalk and talk, PPT, and Group Discussion.

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Elements and Culture. Social Groups- Features, Types and Significance; Culture- definition, features, elements - Symbols, language, values, norms, mores, folkways, fashion and custom

Cultural Diversities- subcultures, ethnocentrism, cultural relativism, cultural shock, Cultural Universalities, Cultural lag, cultural lead and global culture; Social Status Ascribed status, achieved status.

Pedagogy: Chalk and talk, PPT, and Group Discussion.

MODULE - III

8 HRS

Social Process and Interaction

Social Process- Concept, Modes-Competition, Cooperation, Conflict, Accommodation, Assimilation. Socialisation- Definition, goals, biological bases-absence of instinct, social contact, childhood dependency; Agents of Socialisation;

Types of Socialisation-Primary, Secondary, resocialization, desocialization, anticipatory socialization, reverse socialization; Contradictory influences of Socialisation; Social Interaction-Symbolic, Dramaturgy, Ethno Methodology, Social Reality.

Pedagogy: Chalk and talk, PPT, and Group Discussion

MODULE - IV

8 HRS

Segmentation and Change

Social Mobility- Definition, Types of Social Mobility; Social Stratification- Definition, Importance, Forms of Stratification-Social Class, Caste, Consequences of Stratification

Social Change- Definition, Theories, Factors; Social Workers as Change Agent; Role of Change Agents.

Pedagogy: Chalk and talk, PPT, and Group Discussion.

MODULE - V

8 HRS

Indian Polity and Social Issues

State meaning, Function-Protective and Welfare; Forms of Government, Democracy

Social Pathology- Concept, Universality and Locality, Social deviance and Crime, Food Adulteration, Drug Abuse, Domestic Violence, Pollution, Cyber Crime.

Pedagogy: Chalk and talk, PPT, and Group Discussion

References

Abraham, M. F., (2006). *Contemporary Sociology: An Introduction to Concepts and Theory*. Oxford University Press, Delhi, India.

Bhandarkar, D. R., (1989). *Some Aspects of Ancient Indian Culture*. Asian Educational Services.

Bhushan., Vidya., & Sachdeva., D.R., (1989). *An Introduction of Sociology*. Kitab Mahal, Allahabad.

Haralambos, M., Holborn, M., Heald, R., & Trowler, P., (2004). *Sociology: Themes and perspectives*. Oxford University Press, Delhi.

Jayapalan, N., (2001). *Indian society and social institutions*. Volume 1 & 2. Atlantic Publishers & Distributors, New Delhi,

Johnson., & Harry, M., (1995). *Sociology: A Systematic Introduction*. Allied Publishers, New Delhi.

Kapoor, B. K., (2013). *Indian society: Structure and change*. Ritu Publications, Jaipur.

Milner, M., (1994). *Status and sacredness: A general theory of status relations and an analysis of Indian culture*. Oxford University Press, New York.

Patil, S. N., (2007). *Handbook of Sociology*. Vital Publications, Jaipur.

Rao, C. N., (2004). *Sociology of Indian society*. S. Chand Publishing, New Delhi.

Journals

Sociological Bulletin, Triannual, Indian Sociological Society, New Delhi.

Contributions to Indian Sociology (CIS), Sage Publication, Delhi, India.

Indian Journal of Social Development, Council for Social Development, New Delhi

Digital References

Wasburn, P. C., (1984). Socialisation and Social Conflict. *International Review of Modern Sociology*, 14(2), 187–206. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23565702>

Sociology Study Guides- Spark Notes on the concepts of Sociology available at <https://www.sparknotes.com/sociology/social-institutions/context/>

Introduction to Sociology, Rajiv Gandhi University Arunachal Pradesh, India (2016), Vikas Publishing House, Noida available at https://rgu.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Download_636.pdf.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 1

21BSW03(A) EARLY CHILDHOOD DEVELOPMENT

Subject Code	21BSW03(A)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To understand how children develop and the psychological significance of development.
2. To understand the fundamental facts about principles of development.
3. To know how emotions play an important role in children 's lives.
4. To know the contributions of Play.

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to relate the psychological significance of development

CO2. Able to Assess the principles of development.

CO3. Able to examine an important role in children 's lives.

Course content

MODULE – I

8 HRS

Growth and Development, Concept of Growth and Development

Factors influencing Development, Principles of Development

Hazards in Physical Development

Pedagogy: PPT, Group Discussion, Video clips, Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Emotional Development

Characteristic features of Children 's Emotions

Effect of emotions on Children 's Personal and Social adjustments

Hazards in Emotional Development

Causes for behaviour problems in children

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE -III

8 HRS

Play Development - Play – Meaning and Definition

Characteristics of Children 's Play

Contributions of play to Children 's Personality Development.

Hazards in play Development

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - IV

8 HRS

Nurturing Children- Needs of children –Significance, security, acceptance, love, praise and discipline

Art of effective parenting, Components of child- friendly schools

Life skills for effective molding of Behaviour.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - V

8 HRS

Nutrition- Nutritional requirements of infants, pre-school children pregnancy and lactation, modification of normal diets

A brief study of common diseases in childhood (fever, cough, cold, polio, diphtheria, measles, diarrhoea, dysentery, tetanus, eye and ear infection.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

Bettie, B. Young. Keeping your Children Safe: A Practical Guide for Parents. Bombay: St. Paul Publications, 1994.

Chandrashekar, C.R. Know your Child 's Mind, Bangalore: Navakarnataka Publication Pvt. Ltd, 1992.

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Guptha, Sangeetha. The Joy of Parenting. New Delhi: Unicorn Books Pvt. Ltd, 2003.

Hurlock, Elizabeth. Child Development. Sydney: McGraw Hill, 1978.

Hurlock, S B. Child Growth and Psychology. New Delhi: Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company Ltd, 1990.

Lakshamma, T. Professional Training in Social Work. New Delhi: Discovery Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., 2010.

Lions Clubs International and Quest International. The Surprising Years: Understanding Your Changing Adolescent. 1992.

Meyers, G. C. Becoming a Modern Parent. New Delhi: Infinity Books, 2002.

Santrock, John W. Child Development. New Delhi: Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company Ltd, 2007.

Sukhabodhananda, Swami. Art of Wise Parenting. Bangalore: Prasanna Trust, 2006.

Journals

Social Welfare

My Name is Today

Indian Journal of Psychological Counselling

The Indian Journal of Social Work

Modern Practical Psychology

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 1

21BSW03 (B) PRINCIPALS OF MANAGEMENT

Subject Code	21BSW03 (B)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. Understand, and present management principles, processes and procedures in consideration of their effort on individual actions.
2. Participate, summarize and/or lead class discussions, from both the text and student experience that relate to the text material.
3. Knowledge on the Principles of Management will enable the student manager and/ or employee and gain valuable insight into the workings of business and other organizations.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will able to understand present management principles, processes and procedures.

CO2. Able to discussions, case problems and situations from both the text and student experience.

CO3. Identify the Principles of Management will enable the student manager and/ or employee and gain valuable insight into the workings of business and other organizations.

Course content

MODULE I

Introduction to Management: Definition, Meaning

8 HRS

Nature, Features, Objectives, Functions

Managerial, Evolution of Management Thought-

Contribution of Fredrick Taylor, Contribution of Henry Fayol.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE II

8 HRS

Planning: Nature, Importance

Process, Types of Plans. Decision making

Meaning, significance, scientific decision-making process,

Guidelines for effective decision making. Communication.

Process, Types, Barriers of communication, Essentials of Effective communication.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE III

8 HRS

Organizing: Principles of organizing

Types of Organization structure, Line organization.

Functional Organization, Line and staff organization.

Delegation of authority- Barriers to effective delegation

Guidelines for making effective delegation.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE IV

8 HRS

Staffing: Concept of Staffing. Need, Recruitment- Factors, Sources of Recruitment, Techniques. Selection- Scientific Selection Process. Training and Development- Importance, Methods,

Performance Appraisal-Objectives, Methods.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE V

Direction And Control: Meaning, Elements.

8 HRS

Controlling- Meaning, Importance, Techniques.

Motivation- Concept, Importance,

Theories - Maslow's Need Hierarchy theory- Herzberg's

Hygiene theory- McGregor's Theory X and Y.

Leadership Qualities- Leadership Styles.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

Reference

Principles of Management: C.B. Gupta

Management concepts and Practice: B.P Singh and T.N. Chabra

Principles of Management: H Koontz and C.O. Donnel

Management: V.S.P. Rao and V. Harikrishna

Principles of Management: L.M. Prasad

Principles of Management: Tripathi and Reddy

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 1

21BSW04 – Field Practicum – 1

Subject Code	21BSW04	IA Marks	-
Total Contact Hours	16 Hours per week (25 Field work Visits)	Summative Assessment Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	--	Total = 100 Marks	100
Credits	04		

Course Objectives

1. To understand the basics of fieldwork, concept of self and fieldwork and the professional role of social workers.
2. To critically understand and appreciate programmes and projects of governmental and non-governmental organizations.
3. To enhance importance of skills in report writing and documentation

Course Outcome

CO1. To Utilize the concept to field work education to develop self-awareness

CO2. Able to develop skills in field work report writing, record of the observation visits and engage in meaningful discussions during group interactions.

CO3. Able to interpret programmes and projects of governmental and nongovernmental organization

Field Work Contents (Tasks/Activities) – Practical

Field work practicum of First Semester comprises two components:

Orientation Lectures: There shall be a minimum of 10 orientation lecture in the First semester Field work Practicum. This will focus on preparing the students about the field work, concept, definitions, purpose and components, understanding self-awareness and self-management, time management, goal setting, field work practice and ethics, fieldwork record and writing skills and techniques like rapport building, observation and analysis, advocacy, and networking with individual, group and community.

Orientation Visits: There shall be minimum 20 orientation visits in a semester to provide an exposure to and understanding of the services provided in responses to people's needs to governmental and non-governmental organization highlighting the role of social work profession (i.e. agencies in health setting, education, community, institutional and Non-institutional services, criminal justice system, civic administration, rehabilitation, Local bodies, etc.).

Soon after the completion of “orientation visits to fields of social work”, a student conference shall be conducted to share the orientation visit experiences and learning. The students shall record their experiences and leanings of Orientation Visits, which they are expected to produce at the time of viva-voce examination conducted at the end of the semester.

References

- Subedar, I.S. (2001). Field Work Training In Social Work. Jaipur: Rawat Publications
- Sanjoy Roy (2012), Field work in Social Work, Rawat Publication, Jaipur
- Columbia University. (2015), Hand book for Student Social Work Recording, School of Social Work
- Kadushin, Alfred Harkness, Daniel (2005) Supervision in Social Work, New Delhi: Rawat Publication
- Kumar, S. (2002), Methods for Community Participation: A Complete Guide for Practitioners. London: ITDG Publishing.
- Narayana Rao, S. (2002). Counseling and Guidance. Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd
- O'Hagan, Kieran, et al (2003) Competence in Social Work Practice—A Practical Guide for Professionals, London
- Tata Institute of Social Sciences (1998) Field Work Manual for First Year Social Work, Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai

Digital References

- IGNOU School of Social Work (2013), Field Work Practicum in Social Work Part, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a6u_YBsoKCc
- The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda (2019), [https:// www.msubaroda.ac.in/asset/storage/admission/FSW Prospectus 2019.pdf](https://www.msubaroda.ac.in/asset/storage/admission/FSW_Prospectus_2019.pdf)
- Course Outcome based Curriculum Frame work (LOCF) for Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) (2019), https://www.ugc.ac.in/pdfnews/1366718_Social_Work.pdf

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 1

21BSW05 -FUNDAMENTALS OF COMMUNICATION I

Subject Code	21BSW05	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. The objective of this course is to enhance the student's communication skills by giving adequate exposure in listening
2. Improve speaking, reading and writing skills and the related sub-skills.
3. The course is a step towards preparing the learners to face situations with confidence and to seek employment in the modern globalized world.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will heighten their awareness of correct usage of English grammar in writing and speaking.

CO2. Assume their speaking ability in English both in terms of fluency

CO3. Evaluate the comprehensibility in their performance.

Course content

MODULE I

Basics of English Grammar **8HRS**

Parts of speech – noun, pronoun, verbs, adjectives, adverb, prepositions, conjunction, interjections.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE II

Basics of English Grammar II **8HRS**

Sentences- types and construction of sentences, Articles – a, an and the, Phrases clauses and idioms, Wh- questions and question tags.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE III

Literature; **8HRS**

1. The Tyger -William Blake

2. My grandmother's House – Kamala Das

3. I wandered lonely as a cloud – William Wordsworth

4. The road not taken – Robert Frost

5. Sonnet 116 – William Shakespeare

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE IV

Business Communication

8HRS

Introduction, Types of communication,

Barriers to Communication and steps to overcome them,

Importance of effective communication, Cultural differences and Diversity in Communication, body language in professional work environment,

Professional etiquette rules every person should follow.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE V

Writing skills

8HRS

Business writing- minutes, memos

notices, pressie writing, project reports

Informal letters, job applications with resume, Comprehension.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

Reference

1. High School Wren and Martin English Grammar and Composition

2. A practical English grammar- A.J Thomson – Oxford University Press

3. A handbook of English grammar and usage- d thakur – Bharathi Bhawan Publications

4. Writing reports – Seely, John

5. Business Communication: A practice-oriented approach – Shalini Kalia

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 1

21BSW06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW06 K	Kannada I
21BSW06 H	Hindi I
21BSW06 M	Malayalam I
21BSW06 O	Online Mode I

Subject Code	21BSW06	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

(Attached at the end)

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 1

21BSW07 –Digital Proficiency -1

Subject Code	21BSW07	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To understand the importance of technology in social work
2. To practice the digital skills.
3. Using of various mobile apps.

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to identify the importance of digital skills.

CO2. Can apply digital skills in social work Practice.

CO3. To Assess the programs in Computers

Course content

MODULE –I

5 HRS

Introduction, Generation of computers, Classification of computers, Application of computers.

Introduction, Central Processing unit, main memory unit, interconnection of units, communication between various units of a computer system.

Input devices: Introduction, Types of input devices.

Introduction to Microsoft Office, Microsoft Word, Microsoft PowerPoint, Introduction to Libre office. Introduction to a word processor: create and save a document.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Lab and practical

Module -II

3 HRS

Edit and format text: text style (B, I, U), font type, font size, text colour, alignment of text. Format paragraphs with line and/or paragraph spacing. Add headers and footers, numbering pages, grammar and spell check utilities, subscript and superscript, insert symbols, use print preview, and print a document.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Lab and practical.

Module -III

2 HRS

Insert pictures, change the page setting, add bullets and numbering, borders and shading, and insert tables – insert/delete rows and columns, merge and split cells.

Use auto-format, track changes, review comments, use of drawing tools, shapes and

mathematical symbols.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Lab and practical.

Module -IV

5 HRS

Presentation tool: understand the concept of slide shows, basic elements of a slide, different types of slide layouts create and save a presentation, and learn about the different views of a slide set – normal view, slide sorter view and hand-outs.

Edit and format a slide: add titles, subtitles, text, background, and watermark, headers and footers, and slide numbers.

Insert pictures from files, create animations, add sound effects, and rehearse timings.

Spreadsheets: concept of a worksheet and a workbook, create and save a worksheet.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Lab and practical.

Module -V

5 HRS

Working with a spreadsheet: enter numbers, text, date/time, series using auto fill; edit and format a worksheet including changing the colour, size, font, alignment of text; insert and delete cells, rows and columns. Enter a formula using the operators (+, -, *, /), refer to cells, and print a worksheet.

Use simple statistical functions: SUM (), AVERAGE (), MAX (), MIN (), IF () (without compound statements); embed charts of various types: line, pie, scatter, bar and area in a worksheet.

Introduction to Scratch. Drag and drop commands, creating simple scripts, repeating blocks of commands.

Discuss x-y plane, create report. Create a script to draw diagrams using the pen feature.

Internet and Communication: Effective usage of Internet: Email–Gmail, Outlook, Usage of social media for Social Campaign: Facebook, YouTube, LinkedIn, Instagram, Pinterest.

Effective Usage of Digital Technology during Pandemic Situation.

Digital Social Work Zoom, Google Meet, Club House, Microsoft Meet.

Introducing canva – Poster making, Flier, PPT, Effective Usage of Digital Technology during Pandemic Situation.

Digital Social Work Zoom, Google Meet, Club House, Microsoft Meet.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Lab and practical.

References

Laurelet.al., (2019), Teaching Social Work with Digital Technology, CSWE Press

Godfred Boahen (2020), *COVID-19: Using Digital Technology in Relationship-Based Practice to Bridge the Gap in Social Distancing*, Social care institute for excellence, <https://www.scie.org.uk/social-work/digital-capabilities/blogs/covid-digital-technology>

John Hughes (2020), *Zoom vs Microsoft Teams vs Google Meet: Top Video Conferencing Apps Compared*, codinwp, <https://www.codeinwp.com/blog/zoom-vs-microsoft-teams-vs-google-meet/>

Frederic G. (2019), Social Work Education in a Digital World: Technology Standards for Education and Practice, *Journal of Social Work Education*, 55(2):1-13

Digital Reference

Digital Technology and Social Work: <https://www.basw.co.uk/digital-technology-and-social-work-webinar-4-ways-to-use-digital-tools-to-engage-clients.html>

Hong Zhu & Synnøve T (2021) Andersen Digital competence in social work practice and education: experiences from Norway: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/2156857X.2021.1899967>

Digital capabilities for social workers: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ft6kW-GMmIE>
Social work practice with digital communication technologies: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Oja8V5GcoTk>

Digital technologies for social inclusion: <https://www.un.org/development/desa/dspd/2021/02/digital-technologies-for-social-inclusion-2/>

Digital Capabilities for Social Workers: <https://www.scie.org.uk/social-work/digital-capabilities/resources/social-workers>.

A Review of the New Standards for Technology in Social Work Practice <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gj8hvjvkp44>

Future is Bright for AI and Social Work <https://www.cais.usc.edu/news/future-is-bright-for-ai-and-social-work>

Make Time for What Matters Part 2: Using Technology to Improve Efficiency and Developing Strong Relationships <https://schoolsocialwork.net/make-time-for-what-matters-part-2-using-technology-to-improve-efficiency-and-developing-strong-relationships/>

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 1

21BSW08 –Health and Wellness

Subject Code	21BSW08	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours Campus network Based	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To introduce the fundamental concepts of physical education, health and wellness.
2. To provide a general understanding on nutrition, first aid and stress management.
3. To familiarize the students regarding yoga and other activities for developing wellness. As well as to create awareness regarding hypo-kinetic diseases, and various measures of health and wellness assessment.

Course Outcome

CO1. Analyze the importance of Health and wellness

CO2. Defend individual groups and community to maintain sound health.

CO3. Simplify lifestyle and other diseases

Course content

Campus network Based

MODULE –I

3HRS

Introduction to Health and Wellness

Defining Health and Wellness, Personal Health Assessment, Factors Contributing to Health Behavior Change. Dimensions of health and wellness

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion and participation in programmes.

MODULE –II

4HRS

Relationship between lifestyle and health. Physiological and psychological bases of stress. Key components of fitness.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion and participation in programmes

MODULE -III

4HRS

Ways to achieve and maintain ideal body composition Influential Factors for Ideal Body Composition

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion and participation in programmes

MODULE –IV

4HRS

Risk factors and risk reduction strategies associated with the major communicable and

non-communicable disease and threats to health and well-being.

Influences of psycho-social, economic, physical, hereditary, race, gender, and culture on health. Bio-psycho-social model

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion and participation in programmes

MODULE –V

5HRS

Lifestyle Disease and its Management, Lifestyle/Hypo-kinetic Diseases and its Management-Diabetes-Hypertension - Obesity - Osteoporosis - CHD – Back pain Health related Physical Fitness and Assessment Body mass Index/ Skin fold Measurement, BMR, Pulse Rate, Blood Pressure, Health Related Physical Fitness Test.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion and participation in programmes.

References

AAPHERD. “Health Related Physical Fitness Test Manual”. 1980 Published by Association drive Reston Virginia

ACSM Fitness Book, Leisure Press Campaign, Illions, 1996, Leisure Press, Canada
<http://www.pitt.edu/~gsphome>.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 1

21BSW09 BASICS OF NUTRITION

Subject Code	21BSW09	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	---
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	--

Course Objectives

1. Know the role of food in health
2. Obtain knowledge on different food groups, their composition and role in diet
3. Understand different methods of processing, cooking, the basic structure of human digestive system.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will Experiment and become familiar with the terms of nutrition.

CO2. Discover the idea on the concept of health

CO3. Students will be deciding the significance of emotional intelligence in their day-to-day activities.

Course Content

MODULE I

4HRS

Definition of food- food as a source of nutrients; Definition of Health; Dimension of Health – physical, social and mental health

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Practical sessions and competitions.

MODULE II

Food – energy giving, body building and protective; Functions of food- physiological, 3HRS psychological and social; Food pyramid.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Practical sessions and competitions.

MODULE III

4 HRS

Definition of Nutrition; Group of Nutrients – micro and macro nutrients; Diet – balanced diet, metabolism, malnutrition, under nutrition, over nutrition; Is water a nutrient; Deficiency diseases; Relation between food and nutrition, health and diseases.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE IV

4 HRS

Carbohydrates- definition and classification; sources and daily requirements; Lipids – definition, and classification; Proteins – definition and classification: sources and daily requirements; Amino acids – classification, types and functions; Fat – classification and functions.

Food and their nutrient contents; Nutrients present in cereals, millets, pulses nuts and oil seeds, fruits and vegetables, milk and milk products, flesh food, eggs, spices and salt.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE V

Cooking: beneficial and adverse effects of cooking

5 HRS

Different methods of cooking- dry, moist, frying and micro wave cooking- advantage and disadvantage and the effect of various methods of cooking on foods, solar cooking.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion, cooking practices and competitions

References

Passmore R. and Davidson S. (1986) Human nutrition and Dietetics. Liming stone publishers.

Shil's M.E., Alfon J.A., Shike M (1994), Modern nutrition in health and diseases eighth edition.

Shakuntala Manay N - Food Facts and Principles, New Age International Publishers, New Delhi – 110002, 2005.

Srilakshmi B- Food Science, 5th Edition, New Age International Publishers, New Delhi – 110002, 2011.

Mudambi SR and Rajagopal, MV. Fundamentals of Foods and Nutrition, New Age International (P) Ltd., Publishers, 4th edn, New Delhi. 2008.

Manay SN and Shadaksharaswamy M. Foods: Facts and Principles, New Age International (P) Ltd. New Delhi. 2010.

Goleman D (1995) Emotional intelligence: why it can matter more than IQ. Bantam Books

Goleman D (2006) Social intelligence: the new science of social relationships. Bantam Books

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 1

21BSW10 COMMUNICATIVE KANNADA (Only for Non Kannadigas)

Subject Code	21BSW10	IA Marks	-
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	---
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	-
Credits	--	Exam Hours	--

Pedagogy: Communication, Translations and Group discussions.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SECOND SEMESTER

21BSW11 Social Work Methods

Subject Code	21BSW11	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To introduce all the methods in social work
2. To enable the students to have knowledge on techniques in all the methods of social work
3. To develop the skills needed in all the methods of social work

Course Outcome

CO1. The students learn to relate and solve the psycho-social problem of a individual.

CO2. Discover through the interplay of personalities

CO3. To investigate mobilizing resource and need of a community.

Course Content

MODULE -I

8 HRS

Social Case Work-

Definition, objectives, scope, principles and process (study, Diagnosis and intervention) roles of a case worker.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Social Group Work

Definition, objectives and scope, types of groups and group processes –Group work process - roles of a group worker

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -III

8 HRS

Community organization

Definition, objectives and scope, principles and processes - roles of a community organizer.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE – IV

8 HRS

Secondary Method of Social Work

Social Welfare administration Basic administrative practices –social legislation - Importance for socialwork practice.

Social Work Research- Meaning and importance

Social action and its importance for social work practice. social work Research – meaning, aims, Objectives and scope.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE – V

8 HRS

Fields of Social Work

Labour welfare, Medical and Psychiatric social work, community development, correctional social work, Youth welfare and school social work.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

Reference

M S Gore (1969)- social work Education Asia publishing House.

Gisala konpka (1963) - Social group work – A helping process New Jercy: Prentice Hall

Fred Milson (1973)- An Introduction to Group Work Skill, Routledge & Kegan Paul, Boston

Gangrade K D (1971) Community organization in India, Popular Prakasahn, Bombay

Govt. of India, Social (1963) Its role in social welfare New Dehli : Publications

Legislation Division Goal SI & Jain social

Related Online Contents [MOOC, SWAYAM, NPTEL, Websites etc.] jsswnet.com-Journals

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 2

21BSW12 HUMAN GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT

Subject Code	21BSW12	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To understand growth development of the human-Birth to Death
2. Gain knowledge about the behaviour pattern in each stages.
3. To Emirates the hazards in each stage.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students gets acquainted with knowledge about the heredity and development.

CO2. Identify the changes in adolescent, strength and overall health during early Adulthood.

CO3. Influence how to resolve related to the body response to challenging life event during middle age stage.

Course Content

MODULE - I

8 HRS

Stages and Development of Human

Meaning of Growth and Development, Developmental tasks, Developmental Stages: Conception, pregnancy and Delivery. Infancy: Major adjustments of Infancy Babyhood: Emotional behaviour in baby hood- Hazards of Baby hood Early childhood: Emotional and social behavior Late childhood: Emotional and social behavior

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Puberty

Causes and age of puberty- body changes at puberty- effects of puberty changes: Developmental tasks of Adolescence

8 HRS

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -III

Early and Late Adulthood

Developmental task of early adult hood-Vocational, marital, social adjustments- late adulthood –adjustments to parenthood

8 HRS

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -IV

Middle Age-

Developmental tasks of middle age- social adjustment- adjustment to physical changes

Vocational and marital hazards of middle age

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -V

8 HRS

Old Age

Characteristics of old age – developmental tasks of old age, adjustments to retirement- adjustment

tools of spouse – Life hazards of old age

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

Reference

Hurlock E B (1975) Developmental Psychology, Tata McGraw-Hill.

Linda L Davidoff (1976), Introduction to Psychology, McGraw-Hill

Kuppuswamy B (1990), Child Behaviour and Development, Konark Publishers,

Bhatia H R (1972) Abnormal Psychology - Bombay- Oxford IBHPublications.

Related Online Contents [MOOC, SWAYAM, NPTEL, Websites etc.]

[https://www.verywellmind.com/psychosocial-stages-2795743.](https://www.verywellmind.com/psychosocial-stages-2795743)

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 2

21BSW13 (A) HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Subject Code	21BSW13(A)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To enable the students to understand the HR Management and system at various levels in general and in certain specific industries or organizations.
2. It helps the students to focus on and analyse the issues and strategies required to select and develop manpower resources.
3. To understand the job analysis, recruitment and placement process.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will Summaries the practice of HR Management and system at various levels.

CO2. They are able to relate the general and in certain specific industries or organizations.

CO3. They are able to analyse the issues and strategies required to select and develop manpower resources.

Course Content

MODULE - I

8 HRS

Introduction to Human Resource Management

Definition, Meaning of Human Resource Management, Features, Objectives, Scope, Evolution of HRM, Functions –Managerial – Operative, Role of the HR Manager, Qualities of Human Resource Manager.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Case Studies, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Job Analysis and Human Resource Planning

Job Analysis –Meaning, Job Description- Job specification, Job Design- Techniques, HRP- Meaning, Definition, Objectives, Importance of HRP, Process of HRP, Steps to make HRP Effective.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Case Studies, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -III

8 HRS

Recruitment and Selection

Recruitment – Definition, Meaning, Objectives, Factors affecting Recruitment Sources of Recruitment, Selection – Meaning, Essentials, Scientific Selection Process, Placement, Induction.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Case Studies, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE - IV

8 HRS

Absenteeism and Labour Turnover

Concept of Absenteeism- Meaning, Causes, Effects, Measures to Reduce Absenteeism. Labour Turnover – Meaning, Causes, Effects, Measures to Reduce Labour Turnover.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Case Studies, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE – V

8 HRS

Wage and Administration

Compensation Administration-Meaning, Objectives, Factors Influencing wage and salary levels, Methods of Wage Payment-Time Wage Payment, Piece Wage Payment, Concept of Minimum Wages, Fair Wages and Living Wages, Fringe Benefits

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Case Studies, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

Reference:

- Human Resource Management- Text and Cases: VSP Rao
- A Hand Book of Personnel Management Practice: Dale Yolder
- Fundamentals of Human Resource management- T.N. chabra
- Human Resource Management- L.M. Prasad
- Human Resource Management- K.S. Ashwathappa
- Personnel management- C.B.Mamoria
- Personnel and Human Resources Management- P Subba Rao

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 2

21BSW13 (B) YOUTH DEVELOPMENT THROUGH SOCIAL WORK

Subject Code	21BSW13(B)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. Understand the concept and perspective of Youth;
2. Knowledge about the status of youth;
3. The approaches, techniques and models of youth work

Course Outcome

CO1.To apply the concept and perspective of Youth

CO2. Discover about the status of youth, the approaches, techniques and models of youth work

CO3. Assess the strategies by which youth development could be achieved.

Course Content

MODULE – I

8 HRS

Understanding Youth

Defining Youth - Social Construction of Youth –Changing conceptions of Youth. Youth Demographics.

Theories on Adolescence: Hall’s storm and stress model, Blo’s theory of Process of Disengagement by adolescents, Richard Jessor’s Problem behavior theory.

Pedagogy: PPT, Quiz, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE - II

Challenges and Opportunities for Youth

Youth power: youth as social capital - youth as change agents – youth in socio-political movements. Youth in the context of globalization.

8 HRS

Education and Skill Development, Employability and Employment.

Pedagogy: PPT, Quiz, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE - III

Positive Youth Development

Positive Youth Development: Conceptual Understanding of Positive Youth

8 HRS

Development(Competence, Character, Confidence, Connection and Caring).

Pedagogy: PPT, Quiz, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE – IV

8 HRS

Youth Development

Youth Led Development: Concept - Youth Led Sustainable Development in the focus areas of Education and Skill development, Gender equality and Women empowerment, Peace and Non-violence and Climate

Community engagement framework for youth development - Factors promoting and hindering youth engagement in the Community.

Pedagogy: PPT, Quiz, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE – V

8 HRS

Approaches and Models of Youth Work

Nature and definition of Youth Work.

Approaches to Youth Work – Relief based approach, Welfare based approach, Development based approach and Policy Development based approach.

Models of Youth work – Treatment model, Reform model, Advocacy model, Conscientization model.

Pedagogy: PPT, Quiz, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

John Cotterell (2007), Social Networks in Youth and Adolescence, Routledge, London.

Jones Gill, (2009), Youth, Polity Press, UK.

Kehily Jane Mary (Etd.) (2007), Understanding Youth: Perspectives, Identities and Practices, Sage Publication, London.

Landis H. Paul, (2011), Adolescence and Youth: The Process of Maturing, Sarup Book Publishers Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.

M Sarumathi and Kalesh (2007), Youth Policies and Programmes in South Asia Region, RGNIYD Publication, Sriperumbudur.

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Sibereisen K. and Richard M. Lerner. 2007. Approaches to Positive Youth Development. Sage Publications. New Delhi.

Verma.M.L. (2010) Youth and Revolutionary Upsurge, Sarup Book Publishers Pvt.Ltd., New Delhi.

Wood Jason and Hine Jean (2009), Theory and Policy for Practice, Sage Publications New Delhi.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 2

21BSW14 – Field Practicum – II

Subject Code	21BSW14	IA Marks	-
Total Contact Hours	16 Hours per week (25 Field work Visits)	Summative Assessment Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	--	Total = 100 Marks	100
Credits	04		

Course Objectives

1. To understand the basics of fieldwork, concept of self and fieldwork and the professional role of social workers.
2. To critically understand and appreciate programmes and projects of governmental and non-governmental organizations.
3. To enhance importance of skills in report writing and documentation.

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to clarify the concept of field work education to develop self-awareness.

CO2. Able to discover skills in field work report writing, record of the observation visits and engage in meaningful discussions during group interactions.

CO3. Able to assess programmes and projects of governmental and nongovernmental organization

Course Content

Field Work Contents (Tasks/Activities)

Field work practicum of Second Semester comprises Concurrent field work

Concurrent Field Work: The broad aim of concurrent field work practicum is to provide opportunities for applying the knowledge and the information gained in the classroom to reality situations. This learning experience should provide an opportunity of working with communities, groups, individuals/families and managing organization tasks. It is an opportunity to develop intervention skills in reality situations. This entails learning social work practice for two days (16 hours) in every week of the semester.

The student shall complete a minimum of 26 days of visits in a semester. The learners shall be placed in agencies/community to initiate and participate in direct service delivery. Submission of reports to their allotted respective faculty supervisors.

The faculty supervisors through periodic Individual conferences and Group conferences shall assist students to prepare a plan of action for the respective semester fieldwork activities in consultation with agency supervisors.

Workload : *Ratio of Teachers and Students for Social Work practicum shall be 1:8*

*Note: * In concurrent Field Work Programme, every student has to undergo 16 hours of Field Work Practicum per week. Two hours of Field Work Practicum is carried out by the students is equated to one hour of theory classes conducted in the Community/ Agency / Institution setting (16 hours of Field Work i.e. two hours = 1 hour theory class). (16/2 = 8 Hrs. the work load for the Field work practicum shall be considered as 1: 8 The Ratio of one teacher shall has a batch of 8 students) (Each teacher has to spend 1 hour per student. i.e. 8 students = 8 hours per week). As per UGC Model Curriculum for Social Work Education [2001, p. 14].*

References

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Sanjoy Roy (2012), Fieldwork in Social Work, Rawat Publication, Jaipur

Columbia University. (2015), Handbook for Student Social Work Recording, School of Social Work

Kadushin, Alfred Harkness, Daniel (2005) Supervision in Social Work, New Delhi: Rawat Publication

Kumar,S. (2002), Methods for Community Participation: A Complete Guide for Practitioners. London : ITDG Publishing.

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Digital References

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Course Outcome based Curriculum Framework (LOCF) for Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) (2019), https://www.ugc.ac.in/pdfnews/1366718_Social_Work.pdf

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER II

21BSW15 -FUNDAMENTALS OF COMMUNICATION II

Subject Code	21BSW15	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To develop the basic reading and writing skills of first year engineering and technology students.
2. To help learners develop their listening skills, which will, enable them listen to lectures and comprehend them by asking questions; seeking clarifications.
3. To help learners develop their speaking skills and speak fluently in real contexts.

Course Outcome

CO1. Identify the basic principles of communication

CO2. Analyse the various types of communication

CO3. Make use of the essential principles of communication and Identify the prominent methods and models of Communication

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Basics of Communication I

Communication - definition – meaning – elements - basics of communication -

Communication process - importance of communication - the seven C's of communication

Completeness - conciseness – consideration – concreteness – clarity courtesy and correctness.

Barriers to communication - sender-centric – receiver-centric and organizational – socio-Cultural - information overload - overcoming communication barriers.

Practical's: Story framing and narrating (students are asked to frame a story on given topic and narrate it in front of the class)

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Basics of Communication II

Channels of communication - formal and informal – verbal non – verbal - body language -

Sign language -para language circumstantial language - intrapersonal and interpersonal

Communication - group and mass communication - network communication - impact of IT on Communication - pathways of communication - downward – upward - horizontal.

Practical's: Dialogue writing for the given situation (pick a topic on spot and form dialogues and present it like conversation between two people)

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -III

8 HRS

Poetry

Rabindranath Tagore – Leaving this Chanting

William Wordsworth - The World is Too Much with Us

Practical's: Critically analysing the poem. (Analyse the poem in different persons point of view).

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE – IV

Comprehension and free writing

Reading – comprehension-pre-reading-post reading- comprehension questions (multiple choice questions and /or short questions/ open-ended questions)-inductive reading- short narratives and descriptions from newspapers including dialogues and conversations

8 HRS

paragraph writing- free writing, short narrative descriptions using some suggested vocabulary and structures -prepositions, conjunctions Vocabulary development- guessing meanings of words in context.

Practical's: Reading a text and narrating (read any text from magazine, newspaper, comics etc...and summarise it and narrate).

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -V

8 HRS

Grammar and language development

Understanding text structure use of reference words and discourse markers-coherence-

Jumbled sentences Listening – listening to longer texts and filling up the table- product

Description- narratives from different sources. Speaking- asking about routine actions and

Expressing opinions. Language development- degrees of comparison- pronouns- direct vs Indirect questions- Vocabulary development – single word substitutes- adverbs.

Practical's: Advertising a product (form the students in group, give a product ask them to create a advertisement to that product).

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

1. Fisk, J. Introduction to Communicative Studies, 1990. London: Routledge.
2. Aggarwal, Shalini. Essential Communication Skills, 2009. New Delhi: Anne Books.
3. Richards, C. Jack. Interchange Students' Book-2 New Delhi: CUP, 2015

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SEMESTER 2

21BSW16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW16 K	Kannada II
21BSW16 H	Hindi II
21BSW16 M	Malayalam II
21BSW16 O	Online Mode II

Subject Code	21BSW16	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

(Attached at the end)

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SEMESTER 2

21BSW17 -Digital Proficiency -II

Subject Code	21BSW17	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

MODULE –I

4HRS

Browser settings for a secure connection

Working with the operating system: Navigation of the file system using a mouse and keyboard.

Word processing: create a text document; create a letter, report, and greeting card.

Pedagogy: Hands on training, lab and practical sessions

MODULE –II

4HRS

Create a text document with figures in it. It should describe a concept taught in another course.

Pedagogy: Hands on training, lab and practical sessions

MODULE –III

4HRS

Discuss the following in a text document about the basic organisation of a computer:

CPU, memory, input/output devices, hard disk.

Create a text document in an Indian language other than English.

Pedagogy: Hands on training, lab and practical sessions

MODULE –IV

4HRS

Create a presentation.

Create a presentation with animation.

Include existing images/ pictures in a presentation.

Pedagogy: Hands on training, lab and practical sessions

MODULE –V

4 HRS

Animate pictures and text with sound effects in a presentation

Create a simple spreadsheet and perform the following operations: min, max, sum, and average.

Create different types of charts using a spreadsheet: line, bar, area and pie

Pedagogy: Lecture, and Lab/ Practical sessions.

References

Laurelet.al., (2019),Teaching Social Work with Digital Technology, CSWE Press

Godfred Boahen (2020),*COVID-19:Using Digital Technology in Relationship-Based Practice to Bridge the Gapin Social Distancing*, Social care institute for excellence, <https://www.scie.org.uk/social-work/digital-capabilities/blogs/covid-digital-echnology>

John Hughes (2020), *Zoom vs Microsoft Teams vs Google Meet:Top Video Conferencing Apps Compared*, codinwp, <https://www.codeinwp.com/blog/zoom-vs-microsoft-teams-vs-google-meet/>

Frederic G. (2019), Social Work Education in a Digital World: Technology Standards for Education and Practice, *Journal of Social Work Education*, 55(2):1-13.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 2

21BSW18 –Value based NSS Activities

Course Title	NSS Activities	Course Credits	Mode of Delivery
Total Contact Hours	20 Hours Practical	2	Campus Networking Based
Formative Assessment Marks	50 Internal Assessment		

Practical based.

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SEMESTER 2

21BSW19 –LIFE SKILLS

Subject Code	21BSW19	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. Learn each other's' names and qualities and facilitate communication among students
2. Help participants make new friends, and Make rules for the group
3. Identify and clarify expectations ~~and~~the training, develop a sense of trust so thatpersonal growth takes place and understand how some statements can hurt others

Course Outcome

CO1. CO1. Interpret Self-awareness, interpersonalrelationships and communication.

CO2. Discover Self-awareness, critical thinkingand communication

CO3. Assess the skills of Empathy, communication and critical thinking

Course Content

MODULE –I

Getting Started to know each other **4HRS**

Mistaken identities, mime an interest, if you were an animal, Celebrities, Find out, Double wheel. Making ground rules, our expectations.

Only positive strokes allowed, Trust me, Catch me quick, Circle of trust, Secret admirer, Lifeboat.

I Love Myself, My “Protective Shield”, I am Happy to be a Girl/Boy.

Pedagogy: Activity Based, learning by doing, role play and Poster making

MODULE –II

4HRS

My Life Auction, and Values Voting. My River of Life

Act and Meet, Listening, More Listening Skills, Mixed Messages and Choosing Whom to Talk to.

Status and Power, The Chaser, Our Behavior –Passive, Aggressive or Assertive, I and You: Using “I Feel” Statements

Saying “No” and meaning it (includes persuasion).

Pedagogy: Activity Based, learning by doing, role play and Poster making

MODULE –III

Communication and Relationships

5HRS

Relationship Map, The Many Meanings of Love, Obstacle Race, My Best Friend, wanted: Friends Forever, Abuse: Hurting Someone, Hotline, My Family and Me, I Belong to a Community.

Who is right? Who is wrong? Conflict Ladder, Different Perspectives: This and That, Responses to Conflict. Decision Making, Three Cs in Decision-making, Making Ripples: Good and Bad Decisions, delaying sex, Best Response, What Should I do?

Pedagogy: Activity Based, learning by doing, role play and Poster making

MODULE –IV

Problems and Solutions, Excuses, Excuses, You are in the Driver’s Seat, Open Door, and Closed Door, Coping with Emotions and Growing Up, A Book of Me, Happy Memories, A Story of Hope and Big Book, How Different Are We? How is My Body Changing?

Pedagogy: Activity Based, learning by doing, role play and Poster making.

MODULE –V

Substance Use and HIV children- Your Choice of Drugs, Even a Little is Too Much, **4 HRS**

Advertisements Do Not Lie, and The Circle of Hurt

The Immune System Dance, HIV Transmission: Doors of Entry, Stop, Go, Think, Am I at

Risk? and STI Quiz

Goals I Can Reach, How Do I Set My Goals? A “Mantra” for Trying, and Being Responsible.

Pedagogy: Activity Based, learning by doing, role play and Poster making

Reference

Spaargaren, G., and B. VanVliet. 2000. ‘Lifestyle, Consumption and the Environment: The Ecological Modernisation of Domestic Consumption.’ Environmental Politics. 9(1): 50-75.

U.S. Environmental Protection Agency; Backyard Composting: It's Only Natural; October 2009

Delors, Jacques (1997). Learning: The Treasure Within, UNESCO, Paris.

Nair.V. Rajasenan, (2010). Life Skills, Personality and Leadership, Rajiv Gandhi National Institute of Youth Development, Tamil Nadu. Page 8 of 62

UNESCO (2005). Quality Education and Life Skills: Darkar Goals, UNESCO, Paris.

WHO (1999) Partners in Life Skills Education: Conclusions from a MODULE ed Nations Inter-Agency Meeting, WHO, Geneva.

Nair. A. Radhakrishnan, (2010). Life Skills Training for Positive Behaviour, Rajiv Gandhi National Institute of Youth Development, Tamil Nadu.

Santrock W. John (2006). Educational Psychology. (2nd Edn.) New Delhi: Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd.

Life Skills Resource Manual, Schools Total Health Program, (2006). Health Education and Promotion International Inc., Chennai.

Kumar. J. Keval, (2008). Mass Communication in India, JAICO Publication India Pvt. Ltd

21BSW20 COMMUNICATIVE KANNADA-II

Course Title	Communicative Kannada	Course Credits	0	Mode of Delivery
Total Contact Hours	20 Hours	Non-Credit based	-	Online mode

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THIRD SEMESTER

21BSW21 RURAL, URBAN AND TRIBAL COMMUNITY

Subject Code	21BSW21	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To discussed meaning, definitions, various issues of communities
2. To development Various programmes for the community
3. To understand about the various communities, their problems scope to select the research in community studies.

Course Outcome

CO1. The compare the Rural, Tribal and Urban community Development and experiment the pluses of community life.

CO2. The conclude on different types of communities and their life.

CO3. To imagine the characteristics, definitions, problems, and development programmes for the community enlighten them on community life.

Course Content

MODULE – I

8 HRS

Concept of Community- Meaning and definition

Geographical versus functional community, Elements and Characteristics of Community, Community Organization and Community Development.

History of Community Organization in India.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and PPT.

MODULE - II

8 HRS

Definition and Concepts of Rural and Tribal communities

Concept, Definition, and Characteristics of a 'Rural' Community. Types of Indian Villages Concept, Definition, and Characteristics of a 'Tribal' community, Concept and Characteristics of 'Jati' Structure. Conditions Favorable to Caste System, Conditions Responsible for Weakening of Caste System.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE III

8 HRS

Concepts and characteristics of Urban communities

Meaning and definitions of Urban community, Historical Development of Urban Areas, Urbanization and spread of urban communities.

Specific urban communities.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and PPT.

MODULE IV

8 HRS

Major problems and issues of Rural and Tribal communities

Need for the study of rural and tribal communities. Blocks to understand the rural and tribal people, Remedial Measures to overcome rural problems. Major Tribes in India

Major problems & Issues affecting rural and tribal population in India

Poverty and Causes of Poverty.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and PPT.

MODULE V

8 HRS

Problems and its effect on rural and tribal communities.

Human right violation of rural and tribes, The impacts of ecological poverty

Land alienation and bondage, Impact of Liberalization Policies

Globalization: Definition, Various Facts of Globalization.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and PPT.

References

Dmello Laveena (2018) Rural, Tribal and Urban Community Development, Srinivas Publication DB.pdf (688 KB) Submission Id: DB68182.

Thomas William & A.J. Christopher (2011). Rural Development – concept and recent approaches. *Rawat publications*, Jaipur.

Katar Singh (2009). Rural Development, Principles, Policies and Management. *SAGE Publications India Pvt. Ltd.*, New Delhi.

Desai A.R. (1994). Rural sociology in India. *Popular Prakashan*, Mumbai

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SEMESTER 3

21BSW22 COUNSELING AND GUIDENCE

Subject Code	21BSW22	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

- (1) understand the concepts of guidance and counselling
- (2) understand testing and non-testing techniques in guidance service
- (3) understand the types of counseling and qualities of an effective counselor.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will be able to explain the meaning of Guidance, Describe the nature of Guidance and

CO2. Discover the scope of Guidance, explain the structure, purpose of guidance, describe goals of guidance and explain principles of guidance.

CO3. Able to create need of guidance with reference to India.

Course Content

MODULE - I

8HRS

Guidance- Meaning, Nature and Scope

Guidance: Goals and Principles, Need for Guidance with Reference to India.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and PPT.

MODULE -II

8HRS

Guidance Services

Concept and Importance; Services: Placement Service, Follow up service.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and PPT.

MODULE -III

8HRS

Educational and Vocational Guidance

Organizing Guidance Services at School and College Level

Personal and Group Guidance: Concept, Aims and Methods, Personal Guidance at School Level and Personal Guidance at College Level.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and PPT.

MODULE -IV

8HRS

Counseling and Types

Concept, Need and Goals with Reference to India, Counseling: Principles and Counseling Process

Types of Counseling: Directive Counseling, Non-Directive Counseling, Eclectic Counseling, Interview Process in Counseling.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and PPT.

MODULE -V

8HRS

Counseling Services

Individual Counseling, Group Counseling

Organizing Counseling Services at School Level, Organizing Counseling Services at College Level. Problems of Guidance and Counseling.

Psychotherapy: Meaning and Process, Dealing with Psychological Disturbance, Psychotherapy: Cognitive Approach, Environmental Approach; Counselor: Role and Qualities 10 Testing and Non-Testing Techniques: Psychological Tests, Case Study, Rating Scale, Observation, Interview, Inventories.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and PPT.

Reference

Dr. Kulwinder Pal. Guidance and Counseling. DEDU502 Edited USI PUBLICATIONS 2/31, Nehru Enclave, Kalkaji Ext., New Delhi-110019 for Lovely Professional University Phagwara.

D'Mello Laveena (2018). Therapeutic Counseling Intervention, Srinivas Publication, Mangalore, Karnataka. India. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1314178>

Gail Wilson (2010). Understanding Old Age – Critical and Global Perspectives, *London School of Economics and Political Science*, London, 2010.

Ferreira Monica (1995). A Model for the health care management of older people, unpublished paper read at an *International Conference: Dynamic Ageing - The Challenge*, Cape Town, 4-6.

Jeyalakshmi S. Additional Director General, Chakrabarti S., Deputy Director General Gupta Nivedita Gupta Director, Situation Analysis of the Elderly in India.

Hazan Haim, Old Age Constructions and Deconstructions, ISBN: 9780511621925, Cambridge University Press, 2012.

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SEMESTER 3

21BSW23 (A) DISASTER MANAGEMENT

Subject Code	21BSW23 (A)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To understand key concepts and typologies of disasters
2. To understand Processes of disaster mitigation and disaster management
3. To develop Skills and promote intervention strategies to assess the vulnerability and prepare modules for the future eventualities
4. To develop capacity to work with different agencies at international, national and local levels

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to agree the impact of hazards and disaster.

CO2. Able to respond in vulnerable situation.

CO3. Invent strategies to emergency management to restore the quality of life.

Course content

MODULE I

Introduction to Disasters

8HRS

Disaster: Concept, Meaning, and Definition, History of Major Disaster Events in India

Types of Disasters – Natural Disasters: Famine, Drought, Flood, Cyclone, Tsunami, Earthquake. Man-made Disasters: Riots, Blasts, Industrial, Militancy.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation.

MODULE II

Disaster Mitigation and Disaster Management

8HRS

Profile, Forms and Reduction of Vulnerability, Disaster Mitigation: Concept and Principles

Disaster Management: Concept and Principles, Pre-disaster- Prevention and Preparedness.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE III

Impact of Disaster **8HRS**

Physical, Economic, Social, Psycho-socio Aspects, Environmental Impacts

During Disaster- Rescue and Relief, Post-disaster- Rehabilitation and Reconstruction

Victims of Disaster- Children, Elderly, and Women.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE IV

Disaster Process and Intervention **8HRS**

Displacement- Causes, Effects and Impact, Major Issues and Dynamics in the Administration of Rescue, Relief, Reconstruction and Rehabilitation.

Components of Rescue, Relief, Reconstruction; Rehabilitation

Disaster Policy in India; Disaster Management Authority- NDMA, SDMA, DDMA; Disaster Management Act, 2005.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE -V

Role of various agencies **8HRS**

Role of Government organizations, voluntary organizations, local groups.

Community participation, volunteers and social workers.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

Reference

Disaster Management, by Harsh K. Gupta

Disaster Management, written by M. M. Sulphey

Disaster Management, written by Vinod K. Sharma

Natural Hazards and Disaster Management, by R. B. Singh

Disaster Management: A Reader, written by S. Rajagopal

Introduction to Emergency Management, written by Bullock Jane, Daman P. Coppola, and George D. Haddow.

Disaster Science and Management, written by Tushar Bhattacharya

Introduction to Disaster Management, written by Satish Modh

Disaster Management, written by I. Sundar

Disaster Management, written by Dr Mrinalini Pandey

Disaster Management: Future Challenges and Opportunities, written by Jagbir Singh

Disaster management, written by J. P. Singhal

Earth and Atmospheric Disaster Management: Nature and Man-made, written by C. K.

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SEMESTER 3

21BSW23 (B) MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM

Subject Code	21BSW23 (B)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. This Provides the knowledge of contemporary issues related to the field of managing information systems.
2. Develop knowledge and skills required to work effectively in a profession.
3. Enhance self-confidence, ability to make proper decisions and effective communication.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students able to Demonstrate knowledge of contemporary issues related to the field of managing information systems.

CO2. Able to distinguish knowledge and skills required to work effectively.

CO3. Able to adapt self-confidence make proper decisions

Content of Course

MODULE I

8 HRS

The Meaning and Role of MIS

Meaning of MIS? Decision support systems, systems approach, the systems view of business, MIS Organization within the company.

Management Organizational theory and the systems approach: Development of organization theory, management and organizational behaviour.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE II

8 HRS

Database Management

Manager Should Know about Computer Systems: Data processing and the computer, Operation of a manual Information System, Components of a computer system, Conversion of manual to computer-based system. Database Management: The business settings, Objects of DBMS, Database Technical overview.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE III

8 HRS

Information Systems for Decision Making

Evolution of an information system, Basic Information Systems, decision making and MIS, MIS as a technique for making programmed decisions, decision assisting informationsystems. Strategic and project planning for MIS: General business planning, appropriate MIS response.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE IV

8 HRS

Conceptual System Design

Define the problems, set system objectives, establish system constraints, determine information needs, determine information sources, develop alternative conceptual designs and select one, document the system concept.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE V

8 HRS

Implementation, Evaluation and Maintenance of the MIS

Plan the implementation, acquire floor space and plan space layouts, organize for implementation, develop procedures for implementation, train and operating personnel, computer related acquisitions, develop forms for data collection and information, dissemination, develop the files, test the system, cut over, document the system, evaluate the MIS, control and maintain the system.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

Reference

Information Systems for Modern Management- R. G. Murdick, J. E. Ross and J. R. Clagget.

Management Information System: Strategy & Action- Parker, Charles Case, Thomas

Management Information Systems - O' Brien James A

Management Information Systems - Sadagopan S

Management Information Systems - Murdic and Ross

Systems Analysis for Business - Optner

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SEMESTER 3

21BSW24–Field Practicum III

Subject Code	21BSW24	IA Marks	100
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	--	Exam Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	---	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	--

Course Objectives

1. To understand the basics of fieldwork, concept of self and fieldwork and the professional role of social workers.
2. To critically understand and appreciate programmes and projects of governmental and non-governmental organizations.
3. To enhance importance of skills in report writing and documentation

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to compare the concept of field work education to develop self-awareness.

CO2. Able to Analyze skills in field work report writing, record of the observation visits and engage in meaningful discussions during group interactions

CO3. Able to determine programmes and projects of governmental and nongovernmental organization

Course Content

Field Work Contents (Tasks/Activities)

Field work practicum of third Semester comprises Concurrent field work

Concurrent Field Work: The broad aim of concurrent field work practicum is to provide opportunities for applying the knowledge and the information gained in the classroom to reality situations. This learning experience should provide an opportunity of working with community, groups, individuals/families and managing organization tasks. It is an opportunity to develop intervention skills in reality situations. This entails learning social work practice for two days (16 hours) in every week of the semester.

The student shall complete a minimum of 26 days of visits in a semester. The learners shall be placed in agencies/community to initiate and participate in direct service delivery. Submission of reports to their allotted respective faculty supervisors.

The faculty supervisors through periodic Individual conferences and Group conferences shall assist students to prepare a plan of action for the respective semester fieldwork activities in consultation with agency supervisors.

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SEMESTER 3

21BSW25 FUNCTIONAL ENGLISH- I

Subject Code	21BSW25	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. Total shift in pedagogy from lectures-oriented classes to interactive learning
2. To familiarize students with the function of grammatical items used to spoken /written language
3. To train students to use the language with confidence & without committing errors
4. The English Communication skill is to be taught in 2nd semester for all students of Humanities & Social Sciences, to earn two credits.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will heighten their awareness of correct usage of English grammar in writing and speaking.

CO2. They will improve their speaking ability in English both in terms of fluency and comprehensibility in their performance.

CO3. They will give oral presentations and receive feedback on their performance.

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Basics of phonetics.

Listening to texts, listening to CDs, Trials of a good listener.

Pronunciation Introduction to English phonetic Symbols consonants & Vowels with illustrations in use.

Listening & Comprehension Interpretation of texts based on question-answer. Interaction among students.

Reading Skill Techniques of reading. Reading comprehension of unseen pages Identifying the context & the central idea. Vocabulary & word formation from different texts & dictionary

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation.

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Creative writings- Basic Grammar Prescriptive/descriptive approaches grammaticality acceptability –appropriateness-grammar in context grammar in spoken & written Practice.

Exercise on the use of different grammatical constructions in context.

Identification of the use of the above given grammatical devices form different texts like newspapers, poems, stories etc.

Words & phrases used for conversation Making statements, questions, order & suggestions – denying –rejecting-disagreeing-possibility-ability, permission, obligations etc.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE -III

8 HRS

Public Speaking, Public speech.

Dialogues

Telephonic Conversation, Interview etiquette. (Mock interviews, and documentation)

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE – IV

Communicating Through Technology and Employment Communication

Introduction- Classification of Technological Tools for Communication

8 HRS

Major Technological tools- Effective Use of Technology for Communication

Communicating Through social media, Communicating in Virtual Teams. Employment Process. Setting Goals- Understanding Employers 'Mindset towards the Employment Process

Organizing Your Approach to the Employment Process. Drafting Résumés and Other Employment Messages. Drafting Application Letters- Handling Group Discussions

Handling Interviews- Drafting Post-Interview Employment Messages

Pedagogy: Practical, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE -V

8 HRS

Basics of Functional English- An Introduction of the Structures in English Language

Types and Construction of Sentences.

Usage of Parts of Speech and Linkers, Usage of Idioms and Phrases for Standardizing Communication, Accent and Pronunciation for Effective Communication

Explicit Comprehensive Exercises, Implicit Comprehensive Exercises. Converting Titles into meaningful passages.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

Reference

1. Fisk, J. Introduction to Communicative Studies, 1990. London: Routledge.
2. Aggarwal, Shalini. Essential Communication Skills, 2009. New Delhi: Anne Books.
3. Richards, C. Jack. Interchange Students' Book-2 New Delhi: CUP, 2015

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 3

21BSW26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW26 K	Kannada III
21BSW26 H	Hindi III
21BSW26 M	Malayalam III
21BSW26 O	Online Mode III

Subject Code	21BSW26	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

(Attached at the end)

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 3

21BSW27 CYBER CRIME AND SECURITY

Subject Code	21BSW27	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To make understand theEvery organization is responsible for ensuring Cyber Security.
2. The ability to protect its information systems from impairment or even theft is essential to success.
3. Implementing effective security measures will not only offer liability protection; it will also increase efficiency and productivity.

Course outcome

CO1.Examinethe different types of malware and security breaches and develop effective prevention methods which will increase overall security.

CO2. Make use of the basic concepts associated with Cyber Security.

CO3. Design measure to safeguard the information.

Course Content

MODULE - I

4HRS

Introduction to Cyber Crime and law.

Cyber Crimes, Types of Cybercrime

Hacking, Attack vectors, Cyberspace and Criminal Behaviour

Clarification of Terms.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and video Clippings.

MODULE - II

4 HRS

Traditional Problems Associated with Computer Crime

Understanding the Threat from Cyber Crime Introduction Cyber Threat

Definition of Cyber Crime Classification.

Current Threats and Trends, Diversity of Cyber Crime

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and video Clippings.

MODULE – III

Cyber Hate Crimes – Cyber Terrorism.

Responding To Cyber Crime

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and video Clippings.

4HRS

MODULE – IV

4HRS

Cyber Strategy, National Security Strategy, Cyber Security Strategy, Organized Crime Strategy

Cyber Crime Strategy, Policy Cyber Crime, International Response, National Cyber Security Structure.

Strategic Policy Requirements, Police and Crime Commissioners.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and video Clippings.

4 HRS

MODULE – V

Get Safe Online, Cyber Security Guidance for Business, Cyber Crime Investigation Skills, Criminal Investigation

Code of Ethics, Evidence – Hi-Tech Investigations, Capturing and Analysing Digital Evidence.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and video Clippings.

Reference

Thomas Halt, Adam M. Bossler and Kathryn C. Seigfried Spellar, —Cybercrime and Digital Forensics: An Introduction, Routledge Taylor and Francis Group 2017.

Bernadette H Schell, Clemens Martin, —Cybercrimel, ABC – CLIO Inc, California, 2004

Cyber Security: Understanding Cyber Crimes, Computer Forensics and Legal Perspectives, Nina Godbole and Sunil Belapure, Wiley INDIA.

Cyber Security Essentials, James Graham, Richard Howard and Ryan Otson, CRC Press.

Introduction to Cyber Security, Chwan-Hwa(john) Wu, J. David Irwin, CRC Press T&F Group.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 3

21BSW28 Games

Subject Code	21BSW28	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Practical Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

(Participation in the interested games, Campus based)

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 3

21BSW29 Waste Management

Subject Code	21BSW29	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To make them understand the Municipal Solid Waste Management.
2. To know the Characteristics, Health and Environmental Effects.
3. To Give insight on Waste Management.

Course Outcome

CO1. Make use of the Practical experience in Solid waste Management.

CO2.To Assess Waste Disposal techniques.

CO3. To build awareness in the community

Course Content

MODULE –I

4 HRS

Municipal Solid Waste Management, Municipal Solid Waste Management.

Generation and Characteristics of Waste. Health and Environmental Effects.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, visit to plant.

MODULE -II

4 HRS

Waste Collection, Storage and Transport, Waste Collection, Storage and Transport.

Record Keeping, Control, Inventory and Monitoring

Implementing Collection and Transfer System.

Case Study-Waste Storage, Collection and Transport

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, visit to plant.

MODULE -III

4 HRS

Waste Disposal, Waste Disposal - Key issues and features.

Sanitary Landfill. Waste Processing Techniques.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Practical sessions.

MODULE -IV**4 HRS**

Chemical reduction techniques, Volume, size and Chemical reduction techniques.

Source Reduction, Product Recovery and Recycling. Planning of a Recycling Programme. Recycling Programme Elements.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Practical sessions.

MODULE -V**4 HRS**

Composts and Biogas, Recovery of Biological Conversion Products: Composts and Biogas. Composting and Bio gasification: Technology.

Environmental Effects of Composting and Bio gasification. Incineration and Energy Recovery. Hazardous Waste: Management and Treatment.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Practical visits.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)**SEMESTER 3****21BSW30 Communicative Kannada**

21BSW30 Communicative Kannada (Spoken Kannada)		
Number of Theory Credits	Number of lecture hours/Semester	Mode of Delivery
Non-Credit based	-	Blended mode

SEMESTER 4

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

21BSW31 WOMEN AND DEVELOPMENT

Subject Code	21BSW31	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To know the status of the women in India.
2. To understand the violence against women.
3. To know the low status and how to empower them

Course Outcome

- CO1. Analyse the status of the women in India.
- CO2. Assess the disparities against the women in various sector.
- CO3. Decide the various measures to empower the women.

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Women Changing Perspectives-

Demographic composition of women,

Changing perspectives of the roles and obligations of the women through history

Regional variation in sex ratio. Implications of the declining sex ratio.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –II

8 HRS

Division of labour, Sexual Division of Labour

Invisibility of women's work,

self – employed women

Types and specific problems.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –III

8 HRS

Violence against women, Violence against women

Feticide and infanticide, Child marriage, Rape and battering,

Sati, dowry deaths, Sexual harassment.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –IV

8 HRS

Status of Women, Status of women – in Indian society before and after Independence

Gender discrimination, Gender equity, Gender justice

Women empowerment – Theoretical Perspectives.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –V

8 HRS

Empowerment of women, Empowerment of women – Constitutional guarantees, legal provisions. Women welfare programmes – self-help groups

Women protection cells, Mahila policestation – reservations for women.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

References

Brook E. and Davis Ann (1985): Women, the family and Social Work, London, Tavistok Publications;

Everett J: Women and Social Change in India;

Government of India (1974): Towards Equality – A report of the committee of Status of Women in India, Delhi.

Harlambos M and Heard R.M. (1980): Sociology - Themes and Perspective, Oxford Publication.

Jeffrey W Dyer and Raymond T Coward (1992): Gender, Families and Elder Care, Sage Publications.

Uma Shankar Jha and Premalatha Pujari (1996): Indian Women To-day Vol to II, Kanishka Publications.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 4

21BSW32 NGO PROJECT FORMULATION

Subject Code	21BSW32	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To provide background information and tools to guide project identification and formulation.
2. To emphasize the importance of sound selection of alternative means at the early stages of the cycle.
3. To demonstrate how project elements can be clearly specified and risks assessed and reduced.

Course Outcome

CO1. Grasp the main issues and questions in project identification, formulation, and design.

CO2. Summarise the processes of formulating projects, identify Stakeholder's problems and set project objectives

CO3. Ensure alternative means of implementation, appropriate choices made in selecting the best means of achieving given objectives.

Course Content

MODULE -I

8 HRS

Project identification tools, Project identification

Stakeholder analysis, Problem analysis, Objectives, Self-Assessment Questions

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Conceiving alternative solutions, Conceiving alternative solutions

Opening up the alternatives, Logical framework analysis

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -III

Project Design, Introduction

8 HRS

Project design: details of the Log frame approach

The vertical logic: means-ends relationships

The horizontal logic, Assumptions and risks: the external project environment

Self-Assessment Questions

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -IV

8 HRS

Analysis of Factors affecting Sustainability

Section Overview, Section Learning Outcome

SWOT analysis and project sustainability, Self-Assessment Questions

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE - V

8 HRS

Implementation planning – work plans

Section Overview, Section Learning Outcome

Preparing work plans, Self-Assessment Question

Model Projects- Training Rural Health and Environmental Workers

-Awareness Education and Income Generation Programme (IGP)

Model of Covering Letters

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

Reference

Belli P, Anderson JR, Barnum HN, Dixon JA, Tan J (2001) An overview of economic analysis. In: *Economic Analysis of Investment Operations: Analytical Tools and Practical Applications*. The World Bank, Washington DC, pp. 1–7.

Dearden P, Kowalski B (2003) Programme and project cycle management (PPCM): lessons from south and north. *Development in Practice* 13(5) 501–514.

DFID (2003) Logical frameworks. In: *Tools for Development: a Handbook for those Engaged in Development Activity*. UK Department for International Development (DFID), pp. 5.1–5.9.

Potts D (2002) Project identification and formulation. In: Potts D *Project Planning and Analysis for Development*. Lynne Rienner Publishers, London. pp. 23–46.

Sengupta Kalyan (2013). *An Easy Guide o NGO with Society & Trust Regisstration. Book Corporation, Kolkata.*

Stephen T.S. (1994). *Basic Principles of Project Formulation for Voluntry Organization. People's Development Communication- Network, Bhuvaneshwar-06.*

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)
SEMESTER 4
21BSW33 (A) Social Work Research (SWR)

Subject Code	21BSW33 (A)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To introduce social work research methods to social workers.
2. To teach them various methods, types of research.
3. Introduce scientific research data collection methods.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will able to practice the social Work research method.

CO2. They will Examine the statistics and able to use in the research.

CO3. Able to Assess the method of preparing project report.

Course Content

MODULE -1

Research-Meaning and Nature.

8 HRS

Nature and Characteristics, Social Science Research and Social Work Research

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -II

Scientific Methods.

8 HRS

Methods of Research: Historical, Pure and Applied Research, Observation, Survey Method, Case Study and PRA Techniques.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -III

Research Design

8 HRS

Exploratory, Descriptive, Experimental, Diagnostic Research Designs. Steps in Research: Selection of Topic, Formulation of Problem, Identification of Variables – Hypothesis.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -IV

Sampling Methods.

8 HRS

Types and Problems of Sampling – Tools of Research: Observation, Questionnaire and

Interview Schedule. Research Analysis: Sources of Data, Data Collection, Classification, Tabulation, Analysis and Interpretation.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -V

Statistical Methods.

8 HRS

Research Report Preparation.

Averages, Dispersions, Correlation.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

References

“Research Methodology in Social Science Research” by Sadhu Singh, Himalayan Publishing house, New Delhi.

Research Methodology – A Hand Book by R.P.Misra Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi.

Methods and Technique of Social Survey and Research, by Dr. Vatsayayan, Kedar Nath Ram Nath.

Easthope, Gary, History of Social Research Methods, London, Longman, 1974. 10. Bajpai.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 4

21BSW33 (B) E- Business

Subject Code	21BSW33 (B)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. Presents concepts and skills for the strategic use of e-commerce and related information technology from business to consumers.
2. the strategic use of e-commerce and related information technology from business-to-business.
3. Use of e-commerce and related information technology from intra- organization.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will able to Develop the concepts and skills for the strategic use of e-commerce.

CO2. Related information technology from three perspectives: business to consumers, business-to-business.

CO3. Able to Conclude the concept e business and business to business and intra – organisation.

Course Content

MODULE- I

8 HRS

E-Business Framework. Definition, Origin, History of Internet, Working of E-Business, Advantages and Disadvantages

E- Business v/s Traditional Business Mechanism, E-Business opportunities for Business, Goal of E- Business

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - II

8 HRS

E-Business Technology and Infrastructure, Economic Theories of E-Business, Business -to-consumer (B2C) systems and strategies, Business- to- Business (B2B) models and strategies.

Implication of E-Business strategies, Business Applications: Consumer-oriented and Business-oriented E-Business.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - III

8 HRS

E-Business Payments, Introduction to Electronic Payment Systems (EPS), Types of E-Payments: Credit Cards, Smart cards, E-Cash/ Cyber cash

E-cheque, Micro Payment Systems, Characteristics of Electronic Payment systems, Need of EPS System.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - IV

8 HRS

Internet Environment of E-Commerce

Introduction, E-Commerce Security Environment, Security concerns, Types of security vulnerabilities in E-Business

Internet Economy Conceptual Framework, Providers and Vendors of E-Business Software.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - V

8 HRS

E-Commerce in India

State of e-business in India, problems and opportunities in e-commerce in India,

Legal issues and Challenges in Indian Perspective, Role of e- business in India

Scope and future of e-business, Impact of e-business on market and retailers and its social impact.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

E Business R(Evolution) - Daniel Amor, Pearson Edude.

E-Commerce Management – Krishnamurthy

E-Commerce: Strategy, Technologies and Applications - David Whiteley

E-Commerce: A managerial Perspectives - P. T. Joseph

The Complete E- Commerce Book - Jance Reynolds

Beginning Ruby on Rails: E- Commerce – Jarkko Laine.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 4

21BSW34–Field Practicum IV

Subject Code	21BSW34	IA Marks	100
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	--	Exam Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	---	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	--

Course Objectives

1. To understand the basics of fieldwork, concept of self and fieldwork and the professional role of social workers.
2. To critically understand and appreciate programmes and projects of governmental and non-governmental organizations.
3. To enhance importance of skills in report writing and documentation

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to compare the concept of field work education to develop self-awareness.

CO2. Able to Analyze skills in field work report writing, record of the observation visits and engage in meaningful discussions during group interactions

CO3. Able to determine programmes and projects of governmental and nongovernmental organization

Course Content

Field Work Contents (Tasks/Activities)

Field work practicum of fourth Semester comprises Concurrent field work

Concurrent Field Work: The broad aim of concurrent filed work practicum is to provide opportunities for applying the knowledge and the information gained in the classroom to reality situations. This learning experience should provide an opportunities y of working with communit, groups, individuals/families and managing organization tasks. It is an opportunities y to develop intervention skills in reality situations. This entails learning social work practice for two days (16 hours) in every week of the semester.

The student shall complete a minimum of 26 days of visits in a semester. The learners shall be placed in agencies/community to initiate and participate in direct service delivery. Submission of reports to their allotted respective faculty supervisors.

The faculty supervisors through periodic Individual conferences and Group conferences shall assist students to prepare a plan of action for the respective semester fieldwork activities in consultation with agency supervisors.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 4

21BSW35 FUNCTIONAL ENGLISH- II

Subject Code	21BSW35	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To enhance the student's communication skills by giving adequate exposure in listening, speaking, reading and writing skills and the related sub-skills.
2. The course is a step towards preparing the learners to face situations with confidence
3. Able to seek employment in the modern globalized world.

Course Outcome

CO1.Students will heighten their awareness of correct usage of English grammar in writing and speaking.

CO2.They will influence in speaking ability in English both in terms of fluency and comprehensibility in their performance.

CO3.They will defend oral presentations and receive feedback on their performance.

Course Content

MODULE -I

8 HRS

Technical English, Survey Report Writing, meaning of survey, importance of survey, types or 4 basic surveys, structure of a basic survey, presentation and conclusion.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion, Assignment, and Presentation.

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Copy Editing, Scope and needs, Various types of scripts, Qualities and duties of a copy writer, Steps of copy editing, Interaction with the author

Title and cover description- Main features, Incorporating illustrations.

Copy rights, Dealing with Multi authorship, In house manuals. Proof reading and editing.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion, Assignment, and Presentation.

MODULE -III**8 HRS**

Travel Writings, Scope of the writings, role on creative writing, Writing Travelogues.
Writing Travel-Diaries, Writing Blogs on Tourist Attractions etc.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion, Assignment, and Presentation.

MODULE – IV**8 HRS**

Review Writing, Review of TV Shows, Style, Presentation and Technique
Book Review, Film Review Music Review
Review of Any Event.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion, Assignment, and Presentation.

MODULE- V**8 HRS**

Literature Review

Introduction or background information section; the body of the review containing the discussion of sources; and, finally, a conclusion.

Literature review of the poem Ozymandias by P.B Shelly.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion, Assignment, and Presentation.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)**SEMESTER 4****21BSW36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE**

21BSW26 K	Kannada IV
21BSW26 H	Hindi IV
21BSW26 M	Malayalam IV
21BSW26 O	Online Mode IV

Subject Code	21BSW36	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

(Attached at the end)

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 4

21BSW37 ENTREPRENEURSHIP START UP

Subject Code	21BSW37	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To know the interest in the students to start entrepreneurship.
2. To give basic skills required to start entrepreneurship.
3. To share practical knowledge about entrepreneurship

Course outcome

CO1. Identify the interest in the students to start entrepreneurship.

CO 2. To build basic skills required to start entrepreneurship.

CO 3. To measure the practical knowledge about entrepreneurship

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and site visits.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 4

21BSW38 YOGA

Subject Code	21BSW38	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To introduce Yoga and its brief development.
2. To know principles and classifications of Yoga.
3. To teach some Asanas.

Course outcome

CO1.Students will inculcate the practice of Yoga

CO2.They discuss the important of Yoga and the health benefits of Yoga.

CO3.And also motivate and teach others about Yoga.

Course Content

MODULE -I **4 HRS**

Origin of Yoga & its brief development. Meaning of Yoga & its importance

Yoga as a Science of Art (Yoga Philosophy). Meaning of meditation and its types and principles.

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and Lecture.

MODULE -II **4 HRS**

Classification of Yoga/Types of Yoga. Hatha Yoga, Raja Yoga, Laya Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, Gyan Yoga, Karma Yoga. Asthang Yoga.

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and Lecture.

MODULE -III **4 HRS**

Principles of Yogic Practices. Meaning of Asana, its types and principles.

Meaning of Pranayama, its types and principles. Meaning of Kriya its types and principles.

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and Lecture.

MODULE -IV **4 HRS**

Yogic therapies and modern concept of Yoga. Naturopathy, Hydrotherapy, Electrotherapy,

Acupressure, acupuncture. Meaning and importance of prayer.

Different mudras during prayers.

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and Lecture.

MODULE -V **4 HRS**

Effect of Asanas on various Systems. Difference between Asana and Exercise.

Difference between Pranayama and deep breathing. Yogic Diet.

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and Lecture.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 4

21BSW39 INDIAN CONSTITUTION & ENVIRONMENTAL STUDIES

Subject Code	21BSW39	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To Enable the student to understand the importance of constitution
2. To understand the structure of executive, legislature and judiciary.
3. To aware about the environmental Issues.

Course outcome

CO1. Students were able to Interpret the Indian constitution and its structure of executive, legislature and judiciary.

CO2. They were able to address the issues related to environmental Issues.

CO3. Defend the Constitution.

Course Content

MODULE -I

8 HRS

Introduction to the Constitution of India, Nature of the Indian Constitution, Significance of the Indian Constitution, The Making of the Constitution and Salient features of the Constitution, Preamble of the Indian Constitution, Citizenship

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and Group discussions, and Brainstorming sessions.

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Fundamental Rights- Right to Equality, Right to Freedom, Protection of Life and Personal Liberty, right against Exploitation, Right to Freedom of Religion, Cultural and educational rights and right to Constitutional Remedies. Directive Principles of State Policy & Fundamental Duties, Union Executives – President, Prime Minister and Parliament, State Executives – Governor Chief Minister and State Legislature.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and Group discussions, and Brainstorming sessions

MODULE -III

8 HRS

The Union Judiciary-The supreme court of India, The State Judiciary-The High Court of States. Election Commission of India. The Emergency Provisions and the Amendment of the Constitution.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and Group discussions, and Brainstorming sessions

MODULE -IV**8 HRS**

Environmental Studies- Introduction, Definition, Nature, Scope and Importance. Eco System- Concept, Structure, Functions and Components of Eco System. Natural Resources- Forest, Water, Mineral, Food, Energy and Land Resources.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and Group discussions, and Brainstorming sessions

MODULE -V**8 HRS**

Environmental Pollution- Meaning, Definition, Causes, Types: Air Pollution, Water Pollution, Soil Pollution, Marine Pollution, Thermal Pollution and Nuclear hazards. Environmental Issues: Climate Change, Global Warming, Acid Rain, Ozone Layer depletion, Nuclear Accident, Bopal Gas Leakage tragedy and Population Explosion. Legal measures- Environmental Protection Act, Constitutional Provisions and Judicial Remedies.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and Group discussions, and Brainstorming sessions

Reference

- Indian Constitution - D Dbasu
Constitutional Law of India - J.N. Pandey
Constitution law of India - M. P. Jain
The Constitution of India - Dr.ParvathyAppaiha
Environmental Law and Policy in India - Shyam Divan and Armin Rosencranz
Environment and Ecology - MajidHussain

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)**SEMESTER IV****21BSW40 Communicative Kannada**

21BSW40 Communicative Kannada		
Number of Theory Credits	Number of lecture hours/Semester	Mode of Delivery
Non Credit based	-	Online mode

SEMESTER 5

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

21BSW41 CITIZEN PARTICIPATION AND LOCAL SELF GOVERNANCE

Subject Code	21BSW41	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To clear the Concept of citizenship, rights and duties of the citizens.
2. To teach the principles and significance of Panchayat Raj.
3. To make to understand the structure, function and role in Panchayat Raj system.

Course Outcome

CO1. Learner will utilize the system of Panchayat Raj system.

CO2. They are able to evaluate the role of minorities in Panchayat Raj.

CO3. Able to modify the role of a social worker in this system

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Concept of Local Self-Governance

Concept of citizenship, rights and duties of citizens and citizen leadership.

Concept of people's participation, Principles and significance of people's participation. Definition of the term governance and local self-governance

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –II

8 HRS

Panchayat Raj system - Rural Local Government institutions/ Panchayats, Concept

History, The constitution 72nd amendment bill

3rd amendment bill. Panchayat Raj Institutions in Karnataka(1993)

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –III

8 HRS

Structure and Functions of Panchayat Raj System, Structure, functions and finances.

Participation of women, S.C's (Scheduled Caste), Participation of S.T's (Scheduled Tribes). Participation of O.B.C's (other Backward Classes) in Panchayat Raj Institutions.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –IV

8 HRS

Role of Civic Societies in Panchayat Raj System, Significance of Grama Sabha.

Role of civic society organizations.

N.G.O's, media, people based community organizations in good governance.

Factors promoting and hindering civil society participation in governance

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –V

8 HRS

Role of Social workers in promoting participatory good governance.

Direct intervention- work Panchayats, municipalities.

Mobilization and organization- roles in relation to ward committees and Grama Sabha

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 5

21BSW42 SOCIOLOGY AND HEALTH

Subject Code	21BSW42	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To introduce Sociology as a Science of Society and its application.
2. Introduce Sociology and Health related to society
3. Identify the Community Problems and social Culture.

Course Outcome

CO1.Students will able to relate Society and the problems related to their health.

CO2. Able to study the community and the culture.

CO3. Decide the social Problems and social security measures

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Definition of Sociology, Sociology as a science of society, uses of study of sociology, application of knowledge of sociology in physiotherapy.

Socialization: Meaning of Socialization, influence social factors on personality, socialization in hospital, and socialization in rehabilitation of patient.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –II

8 HRS

Social Groups: Concepts of Social Groups.

Influence of Formal and Informal groups on health and sickness.

The role of primary groups and secondary groups in the hospital and rehabilitation setting.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –III

8 HRS

Sociology and health: Social Factors in Health status, social consciousness and perception of illness.

Social consciousness and meaning of illness, decision making in taking treatment.

Intuition of health, their role in the improvement of the people.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –IV

8 HRS

Community: Concept of community, role of rural and urban communities in public health. Role of community in determining beliefs. Practices and home remedies in treatment.

Culture: Components of culture, impact of culture on human behaviour, cultural meaning of sickness;

Response of sickness & choice of treatment, culture induced symptoms and disease, subculture of medical workers.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –V

8 HRS

Social Problems of the disabled: consequences of the following social problems in relation to sickness and disability, remedies to prevent these problems, Population Explosion, Poverty and Unemployment, Beggary, Juvenile Delinquency, Prostitution, Alcoholism, Problems of women in employment.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 5

21BSW43 (A) HEALTH CARE

Subject Code	21BSW43 (A)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To develop an understanding of the Holistic concept of Health.
2. To have understanding of the health situation in India.
3. To develop an understanding about mental disorders and to promote healthy life style.

Course Outcome

CO1.To extend the functions of management and administration of the healthcare

CO2.To Classify healthcare delivery systems.

CO3. To integrate healthcare ethics

Course Content

MODULE- I

8 HRS

Definition, Dimensions of Health, Determinants of Health

Indicators of Health. Mental Health - Warning signals of poor mental health, Causes of mental health problems.

Types of mental illness

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- II

8 HRS

First aid during emergency- contents of the first aid box

First Objects in the ear, nose, eye, Bleeding from nose and bleeding due to other injuries

Bites- snake bite, dog bite, insect bite, Burns, Electric shock, lightning

Fainting, epilepsy, Poisoning - food poisoning

Suffocation – drowning, choking, Fractures, fall and bandages

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- III

8 HRS

Introduction to the systems of medicine – Ayurveda, Allopathy, Homeopathy
Naturopathy and Unani.

Female Health Problems and Home Remedies/Management:

Guidelines for Pregnant Women

Guidelines for Women after Delivery

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- IV

8 HRS

Stress: Definition, Causes of Stress. Physical signals of Stress, Effects of Stress, Simple Ways to Manage Stress

Obesity: Causes for Obesity, Managing Obesity, Cholesterol Management,

Cancer- Causes of Cancer, Prevention and Control

Heart attack: Causes and Prevention, Diabetes Mellitus- Causes, Prevention and Care.

Blood Pressure (BP) & Acidity, Causes, Prevention and Care

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- V

8 HRS

Concept of health care. Levels of Health Care

Principles of Health Care. Health system in India-The central, State, District and Village level

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

Centre for Environment Education. The Green Action Guide. 2nd ed. Ministry of Human Resource Development, Govt. of India, 2006.

Improve your Mental Health and Efficiency. Bangalore: Navakarnataka Publications Pvt. Ltd., 2010.

Chandrashekar, C.R. Mind your Mind. Bangalore: Navakarnataka Publications Pvt. Ltd., 2010.

Goel, Rajnesh. Community Health Care. New Delhi: Deep and Deep Publications, 2008.

Goel, S.L. Health Care Administration: Levels and Aspects. Bangalore: Sterling Publishers Pvt. Ltd., Bangalore, 1984.

Government of India. India Year Book 2014. New Delhi: Ministry of Information and Broadcasting, 2014.

Gulani, K.K. Community Health Nursing: Principles and Practices. New Delhi:Kumar Publishing House, 2009.

Jayaraman, Rukmani. Give Them Facts: Help Them Decide. Chennai: TT Rangahathan Clinical Research Foundation, 2000.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 5

21BSW43 (B) ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT

Subject Code	21BSW43 (B)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. The objective of entrepreneurial development is to motivate a person for entrepreneurial career.
2. Make capable of perceiving and exploiting successfully opportunities for enterprises.
3. To analyze the role of Entrepreneurship in Indian and the economic development with reference to Self-employment development.

Course Outcome

CO1. Learners will able to apply Entrepreneurship's skills.

CO2. Able to examine the project.

CO3. Able to criticize the role of Government in motivating the Entrepreneurship.

Course Content

MODULE- I

8 HRS

Meaning-Concept of Entrepreneurship, History of Entrepreneurship Development.

Role of Entrepreneurship in Indian economic development with reference to Self-employment development.

Concept of Entrepreneurship Development, Attributes and Characteristics of successful Entrepreneur.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- II

Business Idea-Method of generating idea and opportunities recognition

8 HRS

Preparing Business Plan- Meaning, Significance of Business Plan

Components of Business Plan, Business Planning Process

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- III

8 HRS

Technical -Financial- Marketing, Personnel and Management Feasibility

Estimating Financing Funds requirements

Functions and Schemes offered by various commercial banks and financial institutions

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- IV

8 HRS

Role of Central Government and State Government in promoting Entrepreneurship.

Introduction to various incentives, Subsidies and Grants Export Oriented MODULE s

Role of following agencies in the EntrepreneurshipDevelopment.

District Industries Centers, Small Industries.

Service Industries. Entrepreneurship Development of India.

National Institute of Entrepreneurship and small business development.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- V

8 HRS

Role of Entrepreneurship Qualities of Successful Entrepreneurs

Risk faced by the Present Entrepreneur, Reasons for Low/ No Entrepreneurs

Women Entrepreneurs: Role, Problems, Prospects, Social entrepreneurship- Concepts - Importance- Barriers inEntrepreneurship.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

- | | |
|---|---|
| Entrepreneurial Development | -Vasanth Desai |
| Small and Medium Enterprises in India | -Indian Institute ofBanking and Finance |
| Essentials of Business Environment & Entrepreneurship | -Aswathappa K |
| Support System for Entrepreneurs | - Moulik T.K |
| Government as Entrepreneur | - Albert. N |

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 5

21BSW44–Field Practicum V

Subject Code	21BSW44	IA Marks	100
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	--	Exam Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	---	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	--

Course Objectives

1. To understand the basics of fieldwork, concept of self and fieldwork and the professional role of social workers.
2. To critically understand and appreciate programmes and projects of governmental and non-governmental organizations.
3. To enhance importance of skills in report writing and documentation

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to compare the concept of field work education to develop self-awareness.

CO2. Able to Analyze skills in field work report writing, record of the observation visits and engage in meaningful discussions during group interactions

CO3. Able to determine programmes and projects of governmental and nongovernmental organization

Course Content

Field Work Contents (Tasks/Activities)

Field work practicum of fifth Semester comprises Concurrent field work

Concurrent Field Work: The broad aim of concurrent filed work practicum is to provide opportunities for applying the knowledge and the information gained in the classroom to reality situations. This learning experience should provide an opportunities y of working with communit, groups, individuals/families and managing organization tasks. It is an opportunities y to develop intervention skills in reality situations. This entails learning social work practice for two days (16 hours) in every week of the semester.

The student shall complete a minimum of 26 days of visits in a semester. The learners shall be placed in agencies/community to initiate and participate in direct service delivery. Submission of reports to their allotted respective faculty supervisors.

The faculty supervisors through periodic Individual conferences and Group conferences shall assist students to prepare a plan of action for the respective semester fieldwork activities in consultation with agency supervisors.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 5

21BSW45 PUBLIC RELATION

Subject Code	21BSW45	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. This course intends to expose students with the creative and management aspects of Public Relations.
2. The course includes planning and execution of Public Relations campaigns.
3. To know the tools and advertising Public Relations.

Course Outcome

CO1. Learners will able to clarify the concept Public Relations.

CO2. Able to discover the tools of public relation

CO3. Able to decide and manage the events.

Course content

MODULE- I

8 HRS

Public relations – definition – nature, scope and functions

Origin and development of Public Relations in India.

Public Relations Process – fact finding, planning, implementation and evaluation.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- II

8 HRS

Differences among advertising, Publicity

Propaganda, Public opinion

Responsibilities of a Public Relations practitioner

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- III

8 HRS

Tools of Public Relations

Print, Radio, Film, Television

New media, Photography, House journals, Exhibitions, Open House.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- IV

8 HRS

Types of Public Relations. Government, private, public sector

Community relations. Employee relations, media relations

Public Relations in democracy.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- V

8 HRS

Problems and prospects of Public Relations.

Event management, Code of ethics in Public Relations

Professional organizations: PRSI-PRCI – IPRA

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

Bhimani, Rita. (2018). PR2020: The trending practice of public relations.

New Delhi: BEE Books. Reddy, C.V. Narasiman. (2014). *Effective public relations and media strategy* (92nd edition). Delhi: PHI Learning Private Limited.

Sachdeva.S.Iqbal. (2009). *Public Relations: Principles and Practices*. New Delhi: Oxford University Express.

Sardana, C.K. (2000) *Applied public relations in the Indian context*. New Delhi: Harananda Publicaitons.

John Wiley & Sons c. Singh J.K. (2007). *Media and public relations*. NewDelhi: Kul Bhushan Nangia APH.

Smith. D. Ronald. (2009). *Strategic planning for public Relations*. New York:Routledge.

Solis, Brain & Brackenridge, Deirdre. (2009). *Putting the Public Back inPublic Relations*. Upper Saddle River: Pearson Education

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 5

21BSW46 EXCEL AND SPSS

(Online Mode)

Subject Code	21BSW46	IA Marks	
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	-	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	--

Course Objectives

1. This course intends to expose students Excel and SPSS software.
2. The course includes online Platform – SWAYAM.
3. To use tools SPSS in the research.

Course Outcome

CO1. Learners will able to practice EXCEL software.

CO2. Able to do Charts, correlation using SPSS.

CO3. Able to Create data entry of their research by using software.

Course content

(SWAYAM flat form)

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 5

21BSW47 CASE STUDY ON NGO

Subject Code	21BSW47	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Practical Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

(Practical Session on case studies and develop as publishable paper)

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 5

21BSW48 MUSIC/DANCE

Subject Code	21BSW48	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Practical Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

(Participation in the interested music and dance. Campus based)

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 5

21BSW49 Street Play

Subject Code	21BSW49	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Practical Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

(Participation in the interested Street Play with relevant theme, Campus based)

SEMESTER 6

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

21BSW51 Internship & Dissertation to produce a News Magazine & Viva-Voce

Subject Code	21BSW51	<u>IA Marks</u> Internal Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300	300 Marks
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	--	Exam Marks External Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300 Viva-Voce exam = 150	450 Marks
Total Number of Hours Internship & Dissertation to produce a News Magazine & Viva-Voce	320		750 Marks
Credits	28	Total Marks Exam Hours	-

SEMESTER 7

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

21BSW61 SOCIAL CASE WORK

Subject Code	21BSW61	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To understand the case work method and its application in practice.
2. To equip learners with theoretical knowledge for work with individuals and families.
3. To develop competencies in learners to use the method in practice while working with individual clients and families.

Course Outcomes:

CO1. Able to learn values and skills necessary for working with individuals and families.

CO2. Practice the values and principles of working with individuals and families.

CO3. Develop the ability to critically analyse the problems of individuals and families and factors affecting them.

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Introduction to Social Case Work

Introduction to Social Case Work; Social Casework: Meaning, Definitions, Nature

Objectives and Importance, Individual: Nature and Needs,

Problems Faced by Individuals and Families. Historical Development of Social Casework.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –II

8 HRS

Components and Principles of Social Case Work

Components of Social Case Work (Person, Problem, Place, and Process)

Principles of Social Case Work: Individualization, Acceptance, Controlled emotional involvement, Purposeful expression of feelings, Non-judgmental attitude, Client's self-determination, and Confidentiality

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –III

8 HRS

Tools, Techniques and Skills of Social Casework.

Communication: Observation, Listening, Interviewing and Home Visits. Rapport Building and Resource Mobilization.

Casework Relationship, Use of Authority and Advocacy, Recording in Social Casework

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –IV

8 HRS

Process of Social Work: Intake, study, Assessment/ Diagnosis, Treatment/ Intervention, Evaluation, Termination and Follow up.

Meaning various steps Intake meaning, procedure Study–meaning, collecting information. Analysis and assessment–meaning steps Negotiating contract meaning, types, Treatment techniques–supportive and modifying techniques.

Termination–meaning, conditions of termination, evaluation, meaning, importance. Disengaging from relationship Stabilization of change effort. Follow up-Meaning relevance..

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –V

8 HRS

Uses of case work skills in dealing with problems of adolescence

Problems of aged, Couples with marital problems

Case work with HIV Infected patients. Transference and counter transference.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

References

Bhattacharya, Integrated Approach to Social Work in India, Raj Publishing House, Jaipur

Desai, Murali, Ideologies and Social Work, Rawat Publication, Jaipur

Gore, M.S., The Social context of ideology, Sage Publication, New Delhi

Rameshwari, Devi and Ravi Prakash, Social Work practice, Mangal Deep Publication, Jaipur

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 7

21BSW62 SOCIAL GROUP WORK

Subject Code	21BSW62	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To Develop understanding of group work as a method of social work by providing knowledge, skills and techniques required for the Professional Social Workers.
2. The subject gives insights on the techniques of group formation and approaches in group work practices.
3. The topics included for the study will empower the learners to develop required skills in group development.

Course Outcomes

CO1.The learner will apply and practice the method of social Group Work.

CO2. They discover the techniques of group formation and approaches in group work practices.

CO3. Design the skills in group development.

-Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Groups-Introduction, Definitions, Characteristics.

Social Group Work-Introduction, meaning, definitions, Objectives, Scope of Group Work. Significance and Need for Group Work in the Modern Society.

Values of Group Work.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –II

8 HRS

Principles of Group work.Types of Group work- Open and closed groups, Social Treatment Groups (Remedial Groups, Socialisation Groups, Therapeutic Groups)

Task Oriented Groups (Committee, Teams and Councils).

Developmental Groups- Educational Groups; Growth Oriented Groups, Self Help Groups, Social Action Groups.

Pedagogy: PPT, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –III

8 HRS

Group Formation, Development, and process.

Factors of Group Formation- Selection of Group Members (Homogeneity and Heterogeneity), Goal formation, Contract. Steps in Group Development-Initial Phase, Convening, Formation, Conflict- Resolution Mechanism, Maintenance and Termination; Process-Intake, Study, Treatment.

Use of Verbal and Non-Verbal Communications, Evaluation, Termination (Disengaging from relationships, stabilization of change effort)

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –IV

8 HRS

Skills- Facilitation, Analytical Thinking, Communication, Leadership.

Recording in Group Work- Importance of Recording in Group work, Principles of Recording and Types of Recording.

Group Dynamics- Bond, Sub-Groups, Role, Leadership, Isolates, Scapegoats, New comer, Conflict, Decision Making, Group Control, Hostility, Behaviour Contagion.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –V

8 HRS

Programme-Meaning, Features, Importance; Programme Planning, Resource Mobilisation, Skills in organizing Programmes,

Use of Programme Media; Areas of Group work Practice-Health, Education, Substance Abuse, Labour Welfare, Juvenile Delinquency;

Application of Group work to different settings: Children & Adolescents, Elderly

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

References

Group Work Skills & Strategies of Effective Interventions, Brandler S & Roman C.P, The Haworth Press, New York (1999).

Group Work Skills & Strategies for Effective Intervention, Brandler S & Roman C.P, The Haworth Press New York, (1991)

Group Work Reaching Out: People, Places & Power, Garland J.A. New York: The Haworth Press, New York Ed. (1992)

Social Work with Groups, Pepell C.P.& Rothman B, The Haworth Press, New York.

Trecker, H.P (1970). Social Group Work – Principles and Practice, New York: Association Press.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 7

21BSW63 ORGANIZATIONAL PSYCHOLOGY

Subject Code	21BSW63	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To know traits, type, social learning of self and self-actualization theories.
2. Social perception process to understand others accurately
3. Stress and its consequences at individual, group and organizational level, and the power and politics in an organization.

Course Outcomes

CO1. The learners will clarify the various traits, type, social learning of self and self-actualization theories.

CO2. They classify others accurately and overcome the techniques in releasing the Stress and reduce its consequences.

CO3. To design effectively the power and politics in an organization.

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Meaning, Definition, nature and scope; History of Organizational Psychology;

Motivation in Organization: Nature of motivation, Framework of Motivation, importance of motivation, need theories, Maslow's Need Hierarchy, ERG (Existence, Relatedness Growth needs) Goal -Setting theory, Job Enrichment and Job Characteristic Models.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –II

8 HRS

Attitude, definition and nature, Component of Attitude, ABC model, Changing attitudes, Approaches, Characteristics and Attitudinal change.

Recruiting and interviewing- Recruitment, employment interview, selection training and allocation.

Job Analysis- Importance of Job, Job satisfaction, Methods of measuring job satisfaction, Causes and effects of job satisfaction and Organizational commitment.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –III

8 HRS

Types of organization communication, Interpersonal communication, improving employer communication skills

Stress- Nature of stress, Meaning and definition, Effects of stress, Burnouts and its impact and managing stress

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –IV

8 HRS

Leadership: its basic nature, Leadership and Management, Importance of leadership, Leader traits and leader, Leadership styles and their implication, Formal and informal leader and Leader behaviours

Group Behaviour- Group dynamics, factors affecting group performance, teams and group conflicts.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –V

8 HRS

Organizational decision making: its basic nature.

Programmed Vs Non-programmed Decisions, Individual Decision making in Organization,

Organizational impediments in Decision making, Group decisions its advantages and disadvantages and brain storming

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

References

Kumar Anita, Suhail, Pathare, (1995). “Industrial and Organizational Psychology”, Himalaya Publication House, New Delhi.

Ashwathappa K, (2012), “Organizational Behaviour”, Himalaya Publication House, New Delhi.

Ghosh P.K. (2003). “Industrial Psychology”, Himalaya publication House, New Delhi.

Blum M.L., Naylor J.C. (1994). “Industrial Psychology”, CBS Publishers and distributors Nazia Printers House, New Delhi.

SEMESTER 8

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

21BSW71 COMMUNITY ORGANIZATION

Subject Code	21BSW71	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To know the meaning and concept of Community, community organization, Community development and social action.
2. To understand the power structure and problem-solving process in community organization.
3. To study the models of social action, skills and the role of social worker

Course Outcomes

CO1.The learners will able to outline the need of studying the communities.

CO2.To distinguish the types of communities and their problems.

CO3. Able to use the concept of Community, community organization, Community development.

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Meaning and definitions, Geographical versus functional community

Type of Communities- Rural - Definition and Characteristics Communities.

Urban -Concept, Definition and Characteristics Communities.

Community Power Dynamics, Basis of Power Community Power Structure - caste, class, politics and Gender (women). Types of Community leaders Analysis of power dynamic in Indian Communities.

Pedagogy: PPT, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –II

8 HRS

Concept, Definition and Characteristics of a 'Tribal' community

Distinctive Features of Indian Tribes, Concept and Characteristics of 'Jati' Structure

Conditions Favourable to Caste System, Conditions Responsible for Weakening of Caste System.

Pedagogy: PPT, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –III

8 HRS

Need for the study & blocks to understand the rural and tribal people

Major Tribes in India: Gonds, Bhils, Banjaras, Baiga, Badaga, Irula, Khasi, Korwa, Kurumba, Mundas, Oriya, Santhals.

Major problems & Issues affecting rural and tribal population in India: Inequality and discrimination, Poverty, Causes of Poverty: Personal Causes, Geographical Causes, Economic Causes and Social Causes.

Problems and its effect on rural and tribal communities

Pedagogy: PPT, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –IV

8 HRS

Community Organization meaning. Definition and characteristics of community

Historical background of community Organization, Community organization and Community Development. Principles in community organization, Scope of Community organization

Pedagogy: PPT, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –V

8 HRS

Techniques of Community study, Community work process, Stages of community organization process.

Roles of a community organizer and Skills required for a community organizer.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

References

1. Ross, Murray. G. (1955). Community Organisation Theory and Principles, Harper Bros, New York. Rothman, Jack & Erlich, John, L. & Tropman, John. E. (2001).
2. Siddiqui, H.Y. (1997). Working with Communities, Hira Publications, New Delhi. Weil, Marie. (Ed.). The Handbook of Community Practice, Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks.
3. Parker, Jonathan and Bradley Greta: Social Work Practice: Assessment, Planning, Intervention and Review, UK:
4. Laveena D'Mello (2018). Community Development-Rural, Urban, and a Tribal Perseptive. *FSP Media Publications*, ISBN: 978-1-5457-2306-7.

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 8

21BSW72 SOCIAL ACTION AND SOCIAL WELFARE ADMINISTRATION

Subject Code	21BSW72	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To know the meaning and concept of Social Action a Method of social work.
2. To understand the Tactics and Techniques of Social Action.
3. To analyze the role of social worker in social action.

Course Outcomes

CO1. The learners will be able to clarify the need of social action as a method of problem solving.

CO2. To discover new ways to sensitize the people in respect to social action.

CO3. Able to imagine the concept of social action in Community development.

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Social Action: Concepts and Related Terms, History of Social Action.

Scope and Relevance of Social Action.

Integrated approach to social work and social action, understanding various systems-change agent, client, target, action systems, Process of change effort.

Pedagogy: PPT, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –II

8 HRS

Role of social worker, Social action in relation to community organization

Values and ethics of social action, Principles of social action.

Models of social action- Elitist social action model, popular social action model.

Gandhian model of social action.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –III

8 HRS

Strategies and tactics in social action, planning strategies

Mobilization strategies: Advocacy, Bureaucracy advocacy, Media Advocacy,

Skills in social action, Social action and social movement.

Pedagogy: PPT, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –IV

8 HRS

Social Welfare Administration: Concept, History and Nature.

Concepts Related to Social Welfare Administration, Definition of Social Welfare Administration. Features of Social Welfare Administration, History of Social Welfare Administration in India.

Nature of Social Welfare Administration, Social Welfare Administration as a Profession

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –V

8 HRS

Functions of Social Welfare Administration, Principles of Social Welfare Administration

Scope of Social Welfare Administration, The POSDCoRB view

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

References

Murphy, Patricia. Watkins & Cunningham, James V. (2003). Organising for Community Controlled Development: Renewing Civil Society, Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks.

Ross, Murray. G. (1955). Community Organisation Theory and Principles, Harper Bros, New York. Rothman, Jack & Erlich, John, L. & Tropman, John. E. (2001).

Siddiqui, H.Y. (1997). Working with Communities, Hira Publications, New Delhi. Weil, Marie. (Ed.). The Handbook of Community Practice, Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks.

Chakraborty, Somen, (1999): A Critique of Social Movements in India, Indian Social Institute

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

SEMESTER 8

21BSW73 GERONTOLOGICAL SOCIAL WORK

Subject Code	21BSW73	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To know about the problems and issues of elderly.
2. Introduce the policies and law related to elderly abuse.
3. To understand the services for the elderly.

Course Outcomes

CO1. The learners will be able to understand better the problems and issues of elderly.

CO2. Able to share their knowledge with elderly on the policies and law related to them.

CO3. Able to gain knowledge on the services for the elderly.

Course content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Definition of the aged, concepts of Geriatrics and Gerontology

The demographic profile of elderly

Ageing trends of increasing Ageing Population in India.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –II

8 HRS

Theoretical Perspectives on Ageing:

Engagement theory, Disengagement theory

Activity theory, Modernization theory

Labelling theory – importance of Gerontological Social Work.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE –III

8 HRS

Problems of the elderly – Social, Economic, Health Psychological, Familial; neglect and abuse of the elderly.

Status of the aged in traditional and modern society.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –IV

8 HRS

Aged related policies and laws for education

Employment, Retirement, Social Security and Pension.

National Policy for Older Persons 1999.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE –V

8 HRS

Services for the elderly – constitutional and legislative provisions for the welfare of the elderly

Institutional and non- Institutional services for the elderly

Role of Governmental and non-Governmental Organizations for the Welfare of the aged.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Video and screening of short films.

References

1. Sharama M.L. and Dak T.M. (ed) (1987): Aging in India, New Delhi: Ajanta Publication, Delhi.
2. Desai K.G. (1982): Aging in India, Mumbai, TISS.
3. Gajindragadkar (ed) (1983): Disabled in India, Mumbai, Somaiya Publications.
4. Leus V (1987): Development and Handicap New York: Bahi Blockwell Inc.
5. Marshal M (1983): Social Work with the Disabled London, Macmillan.
6. Shubha, S et al (2000): Senior Citizens Guide, New Delhi: Help Age.
7. Bhatia, H.S. (1983) Aging and Society: A Sociological study of Retired Public Servants, the Aryas Book Centre Publishers, Udaipur.
9. Nair, S.B. (1990): Social Security and the weaker Sections. A Study of Old Women Agricultural Workers in Kerala, Penaisance Publishing House, Delhi.

First semester – Kannada syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW06 K/ 21BAJ06 K	Kannada I
21BSW06 H/ 21BAJ06 H	Hindi I
21BSW06 M/ 21BAJ06 M	Malayalam I
21BSW06 O/ 21BAJ06 O	Online Mode I

Subject Code	21BSW06/ 21BAJ06	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

ಪದ್ಯ ಭಾಗ

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| ೧. ಕುರುರಾಜಂ ಮಾನಹಾನಿಗೆ ನೊಂದಂ | - ರನ್ನ |
| ೨. ತಿರುಕೊಳವಿನಾಚಿಯ ಪ್ರಲಾಪ | - ಷಡಕ್ಷರದೇವ |
| ೩. ಜೀವಪರ ನಿಲುವಿನ ವಚನಗಳು | - ಬಸವಣ್ಣ |
| ೪. ಮಾದ ಮಾದಿ | - ಬಿ. ಎಂ. ಶ್ರೀ. |
| ೫. ಬರತಿರೇನ ಪಂಥರಪುರಕ | - ಸವದತ್ತಿ ಸಿದ್ದಪ್ಪ |
| ೬. ಹಳ್ಳಿ ಪ್ಯಾಟಿ ಕದನ | - ಮಲ್ಲ ಬಸವ |
| ೭. ತಿಳಿದವರೇ ಹೇಳಿ | - ವೈದೇಹಿ |
| ೮ ಕಟ್ಟಿತೇವ ನಾವು | - ಸತೀಶ ಕುಲಕರ್ಣಿ |
| ೯. ಬುದ್ಧನಿಗೊಂದಿಷ್ಟು ದಾರಿ ಬಿಡಿ | - ಸತ್ಯಾನಂದ ಪಾತ್ರೋಟ |

ಗದ್ಯ ಭಾಗ

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| ೧೦. ಸುಮತಿ ಕಥೆ | - ಶಿವಕೋಟ್ಯಾಚಾರ್ಯ |
| ೧೧. ಅಡ್ಡ ಹೆಸರು | - ಡಾ. ಎಂ. ಎಂ. ಕಲಬುರ್ಗಿ |
| ೧೨. ಕನ್ನಡ ರಂಗಭೂಮಿ | - ಡಾ. ಬಾಳಣ್ಣ ಸೀಗೆಹಳ್ಳಿ |
| ೧೩. ಸಂತ ಕವಿ ಅಮೀರ್ ಖುಸ್ರೋ | - ಫಕೀರ ಮಹ್ಮದ ಕಟ್ಟಾಡಿ |
| ೧೪. ಹುಳಿಮಾವಿನ ಮರ ಮತ್ತು ನಾನು | - ಇಂದಿರಾ ಲಂಕೇಶ |
| ೧೫. ಹಟ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹುಟ್ಟಿದ ಕನ್ನಡ | - ಡಾ. ಮೊಗ್ಗಿ ಗಣೇಶ |
| ೧೬. ಭವದ ಬೀಜ ಮೊಳೆವಲ್ಲಿ | - ಚನ್ನಪ್ಪ ಅಂಗಡಿ |

Second semester – Kannada syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW16 K/ 21BAJ16 K	Kannada II
21BSW16 H/ 21BAJ16 H	Hindi II
21BSW16 M/ 21BAJ16 M	Malayalam II
21BSW16 O/ 21BAJ16 O	Online Mode II

Subject Code	21BSW16/ 21BAJ16	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

ಪದ್ಯ ಭಾಗ

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| ೧. ಧನ್ವಂತರಿ ಕಥೆ | - ನಯಸೇನ |
| ೨. ವಚನಗಳು | - ವಚನಕಾರರು |
| ೩. ತನುವ ನೀರೊಳಗದ್ದಿ ಫಲವೇನು? | - ಪುರಂದರದಾಸರು |
| ೪. ಬುದ್ಧ | - ಅಂಬಿಕಾತನಯದತ್ತ |
| ೫. ನಾಜೂಕದ ನಾರಿ | - ಬೆಟಗೇರಿ ಕೃಷ್ಣಶರ್ಮ |
| ೬. ಅನ್ವೇಷಣೆ | - ಜಿ. ಎಸ್. ಶಿವರುದ್ರಪ್ಪ |
| ೭. ಅಗಸ್ತ್ಯ ಹದಿನೈದು | -ಚಂದ್ರಶೇಖರ ಪಾಟೀಲ |
| ೮. ಹಸಿದ ಹೊಟ್ಟೆಯ ಹಾಡು | -ಅನಸೂಯಾ ಕಾಂಬಳೆ |

ಗದ್ಯ ಭಾಗ

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| ೯. ಗೆಲವು | -ಮಿರ್ಜಿ ಅಣ್ಣಾರಾಯ |
| ೧೦. ಪರಿಸರ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆ | -ಡಾ. ಶಿವರಾಮ ಕಾರಂತ |
| ೧೧. ಶಬರಿಗಾದನು ಅತಿಥಿ ದಾಶರಥಿ | -ದೇ. ಜವರೇಗೌಡ |
| ೧೨. ಹೊಸ ದಿಕ್ಕಿನೆಡೆಗೆ | -ಅಪ್ಪಾರಾಯ ಎಂ. ಮದರಿ |
| ೧೩. ಕಾಗಿ ಶಕುನ | -ಡಾ. ಎಚ್. ಟಿ. ಪೋಲೆ |
| ೧೪. ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಸಂಗ್ರಾಮದ ಬೆಳ್ಳಿಚುಕ್ಕೆ: ಕಿತ್ತೂರು ರಾಣಿ ಚೆನ್ನಮ್ಮ | -ಮನು ಬಳಿಗಾರ್ |
| ೧೫. ಆರ್ತನಾದ | -ಮೂಲ: ಇರಾವತಿ ಕವಕನ್ನಡಕ್ಕೆ:
ಚಂದ್ರಕಾಂತ ಪೋಕಳೆ |
| ೧೬. ಸರ್ಕಸ್ | -ಬಸವಣ್ಣಪ್ಪಾ ಕಂಬಾರ |

Third semester –Kannada syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW26 K/ 21BAJ26 K	Kannada III
21BSW26 H/ 21BAJ26 H	Hindi III
21BSW26 M/ 21BAJ26 M	Malayalam III
21BSW26 O/ 21BAJ26 O	Online Mode III

Subject Code	21BSW26/ 21BAJ26	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

ಪ್ರಾಚಾರ್ಯರು ಪ್ರಾಚಾರ್ಯರು ಪ್ರಾಚಾರ್ಯರು

ನಿಗದಿತ ಪಾಠಗಳು

ಅಂಕಗಳು: ೨೪

೧. ಉಪರಂಭಿಯ ಪ್ರಸಂಗ - ನಾಗಚಂದ್ರ
೨. ನಾವು ಸಾರಥಿಯಾದೆವು - ಕುಮಾರವ್ಯಾಸ
೩. ವ್ರೀಹಿ -ನರೆದಲೆಗೆ ವಾಗ್ವಾದ- ಕನಕದಾಸ
೪. ತರವಲ್ಲ ತಗಿ ನಿನ್ನ ತಂಬೂರಿ - ಶಿಶುನಾಳ ಶರೀಫ
೫. ನಾವೆಲ್ಲರೂ ಒಂದೆ ಜಾತಿ - ಎಂ. ಗೋಪಾಲಕೃಷ್ಣ ಅಡಿಗ
೬. ಕುರಿಗಳು ಸಾರ್ ಕುರಿಗಳು - ಕೆ. ಎಸ್. ನಿಸಾರ್ ಅಹಮದ್
೭. ಎನ್ನ ದೇವರ ಗುಡಿ- ಅಮೃತ ಸೋಮೇಶ್ವರ
೮. ಅಪ್ಪನಿಗೆ ಒಂದು ಪತ್ರ- ಎಚ್. ಗೋವಿಂದಯ್ಯ
೯. ಎರಡು ಭೂರ್ಜ ಪತ್ರಗಳು - ಸ. ಉಷಾ
೧೦. ಲೈನ್‌ಮನ್ ಮಡಿವಾಳ ಭೀಮಪ್ಪನಿಗೆ- ಸತೀಶ ಕುಲಕರ್ಣಿ
೧೧. ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳಿರುವುದು ಶೇಕ್ಸ್‌ಪಿಯರನಿಗೆ - ಜಿ.ಎನ್. ಮೋಹನ್
೧೨. ಪಾಂಡವರ ಅಜ್ಞಾತವಾಸ- ಜನಪದ

ಪಠ್ಯ ೨ - ಚಂದಳರು (ಪ್ರಬಂಧಗಳು)

ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಸಂಪಾದಕರು: ಡಾ. ಕೆ.ಅಭಯಕುಮಾರ್

ಸಂಪಾದಕರು: ಪ್ರೊ.ಎನ್.ಭವಾನಿಶಂಕರ ರಾವ್, ಶ್ರೀ ಮೋಹನದಾಸ್, ಶ್ರೀ ಕೇಶವ ಎಚ್.

ಪ್ರಕಾಶಕರು: ಪ್ರಸಾರಾಂಗ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾನಿಲಯ, ೨೦೧೦

Fourth semester – Kannada syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW36 K/ 21BAJ36 K	Kannada IV
21BSW36 H/ 21BAJ36 H	Hindi IV
21BSW36 M/ 21BAJ36 M	Malayalam IV
21BSW36 O/ 21BAJ36 O	Online Mode IV

Subject Code	21BSW36/ 21BAJ36	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

ನಿಗದಿತ ಪಾಠಗಳು

ಅಂಕಗಳು: ೨೪

೧. ಕನ್ನಡ ಮೌಲ್ಯ - ಗೊರೂರು ರಾಮಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಆಯ್ಯಂಗಾರ್
೨. ಹಳ್ಳಿಗರೊಡನೆ ಸಾಕ್ರಟಿಸ್- ರಂಜಾನ್ ದರ್ಗಾ
೩. ನುಂಗಲಾರದ ತುತ್ತು- ಕೆ.ಪಿ.ಪೂರ್ಣಚಂದ್ರ ತೇಜಸ್ವಿ
೪. ಓಬಾಮ-ನೀನು ಅಮೆರಿಕವನ್ನು ಬದಲಿಸಬಲ್ಲೆಯೆ? - ಡಾ.ಮುಜ್ಜಾಫರ್ ಅಸ್ಸಾದಿ
೫. ಪೂರ್ವದ ಅಪೂರ್ವ ಹಾಂಗ್‌ಕಾಂಗ್- ನಾಗೇಶ್ ಹೆಗ್ಡೆ
೬. ರತ್ನಗರ್ಭಾ ವಸುಂಧರಾ- ನಳಿನಿ ಮೂರ್ತಿ

ಪಠ್ಯ ೩ -ಚಂದಳಿರು (ಕಥೆಗಳು)

ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಸಂಪಾದಕರು: ಡಾ. ಕೆ.ಅಭಯ ಕುಮಾರ್
ಸಂಪಾದಕರು: ಪ್ರೊ.ಎನ್.ಭವಾನಿಶಂಕರ ರಾವ್, ಶ್ರೀ ಮೋಹನದಾಸ್, ಶ್ರೀ ಕೇಶವ ಎಚ್.
ಪ್ರಕಾಶಕರು: ಪ್ರಸಾರಾಂಗ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾನಿಲಯ, ೨೦೧೦

ನಿಗದಿತ ಪಾಠಗಳು

ಅಂಕಗಳು: ೧೬

೧. ಮೋಚಿ - ಭಾರತೀಪ್ರಿಯ
೨. ಅಂಗಡಿ ಪೂಜೆ - ಆರ್. ವಿ.ಭಂಡಾರಿ
೩. ಕಣ್ಣಪ್ಪನ ಅಂತಿಮ ದಿನಗಳು- ಪಿ. ಲಂಕೇಶ್
೪. ಬಿತ್ತಿ ಬೆಳೆದವರು- ಸಾರಾ ಅಬೂಬಕರ್

ಪಠ್ಯ ೪- (ಕಾದಂಬರಿ) ಮಾಧವಿ -ಅನುಪಮ ನಿರಂಜನ

ಅಂಕಗಳು -೧೬

ಪ್ರಕಾಶಕರು: ಡಿ.ವಿ.ಕೆ.ಮೂರ್ತಿ, ಮೈಸೂರು; ೧೯೭೬

First semester – Hindi syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW06/21BAJ06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW06 K/ 21BAJ06 K	Kannada I
21BSW06 H/ 21BAJ06 H	Hindi I
21BSW06 M/ 21BAJ06 M	Malayalam I
21BSW06 O/ 21BAJ06 O	Online Mode I

Subject Code	21BSW06/ 21BAJ06	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

I. कालजयी कहानियाँ (कहानी संग्रह)

2x12=24 Hr

- 1) चंद्रधर शर्मा गुलेरी – उसने कहा था 2) प्रेमचन्द – कफन 3) यशपाल–परदा
- 4) भीष्म साहनी –चीफ की दावत 5) उषा प्रियंवदा– वापसी 6)जयशंकर प्रसाद – गुण्डा
- 7) फणीश्वरनाथ रेणु – पंचलाइट, 8) अज्ञेय – रोज़ 9) मोहन राकेश – मालवी
- 10) कमलेश्वर – दिल्ली में एक मौत

II कालजयी लघु कथाएँ (लघु कथा संग्रह)

1x12=12 Hr

प्रेमचंद, नासिरा शर्मा, असगर वजाहत, चित्रा मुद्गल, सुकेश साहनी, बलराम, महेश–दर्पण

III. गबन – प्रेमचन्द (उपन्यास)

3x12=36 Hr

Prescribed Books:

- 1) कालजयी कहानियाँ – सं. वी. कुमार, लोकभारती प्रकाशन, इलाहाबाद
- 2) गबन – प्रेमचन्द, जगत भारती प्रकाशन , इलाहाबाद
- 3) कालजयी लघु कथाएँ (लघु कथा संग्रह) सुमित्र प्रकाशन,दिल्ली

Second semester – Hindi Syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW16 K/ 21BAJ16 K	Kannada II
21BSW16 H/ 21BAJ16 H	Hindi II
21BSW16 M/ 21BAJ16 M	Malayalam II
21BSW16 O/ 21BAJ16 O	Online Mode II

Subject Code	21BSW16/ 21BAJ16	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Unit 1 : मध्य कालीन काव्य :

अ 1तुलसीदास -बालकांड, अरण्यकांड, सुंदरकांड, लंका कांड, अयोध्या कांड, अरण्यकांड, किष्किंधा कांड, उत्तरकांड।

आ, 2. मीराबाई की पदावली।

इस, 3. रहीम के दोहे.

Unit 2. आधुनिक काव्य,

अ जयशंकर प्रसाद , -ले चल वहां भुलावा देकर।

2. सूर्यकांत त्रिपाठी निराला,--बादल राग।

3. नागार्जुन, --मास्टर।

4. केदारनाथ सिम्हा--कमरे का दानव।

Unit 3. कहानियां ।

1. महादेवी वर्मा,--गौरा गाय (रेखाचित्र) .

2. अमरकांत ,--दोपहर का भोजन।

Unit 4. व्याकरण।

1. पत्र लेखन, 2. विज्ञापन, 3. भेंट वार्ता, 4. स्ववृत्त लेखन। (नौकरी और विवाह के लिए)।

5. वाक्य परिवर्तन,--(काल के आधार पर)।

Third semester –Hindi syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW26 K/ 21BAJ26 K	Kannada III
21BSW26 H/ 21BAJ26 H	Hindi III
21BSW26 M/ 21BAJ26 M	Malayalam III
21BSW26 O/ 21BAJ26 O	Online Mode III

Subject Code	21BSW26/ 21BAJ26	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

II. हिन्दी कविता (काव्य संग्रह)

2x12=24 Hr

- 1) कबीरदास – साँच कौ अंग, भेष कौ अंग 2)सूरदास – गोकुल लीला 3) तुलसीदास – दोहावली
- 4) बिहारी – छन्द

II. आधुनिक हिन्दी कविता

2x12=24 Hr

1. मैथिलीशरण गुप्त- मातृभूमि, मनुष्यता, भारत-भारती .2 जयशंकर प्रसाद – बड़े चलो, बीती विभावरी, जाग री – श्रद्धा सर्ग
2. सूर्यकान्त त्रिपाठी निराला – वर दे वीणा वादिनी ,संध्या सुंदरी, राम की शक्ति पूजा
3. सुमित्रानन्दन पंत – मोह, संध्या, गा कोकिल
4. महादेवी वर्मा – वे मुस्कयते फूल, जो तुम आ जाते एक बार
5. रामधारी सिंह दिनकर – हिमालय, अभिनव मनुष्य, चाँद और कवि
6. केदारनाथ अग्रवाल – बसन्ती हवा, धरती, हिन्दी

III. गीत पुंज (गीति काव्य)

2x12=24 Hr

- 1) गोपालदास नीरज – जीवन नहीं मरा करता है 2) ज्ञानवती सक्सेना – जीवन अनुभव पुस्तक
- 3) डॉ. सरिता शर्मा – बेटी 4) बालकवि बैरागी – अपनी गंध नहीं बेचूँगा

Prescribed Books:

- 1) हिंदी कविता- सं डॉ. नामदेव, डॉ. नीलम अक्षर पब्लिशर्स, दिल्ली
- 2) आधुनिक हिन्दी कविता – डॉ. नागरत्ना, डॉ. सुमा टी. आर., वाणी प्रकाशन, दिल्ली
- 3) गीत पुंज – डॉ. विष्णु सरवदे, राजकमल प्रकाशन , दिल्ली

Fourth semester – Kannada syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW36 K/ 21BAJ36 K	Kannada IV
21BSW36 H/ 21BAJ36 H	Hindi IV
21BSW36 M/ 21BAJ36 M	Malayalam IV
21BSW36 O/ 21BAJ36 O	Online Mode IV

Subject Code	21BSW36/ 21BAJ36	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

I. युगे-युगे क्रांति- विष्णु प्रभाकर (नाटक)

2x12=24 Hr

II. एकांकी संगम (एकांकी संग्रह)

2x12=24 Hr

1. रामकुमार वर्मा – घर का मकान
2. जगदीशचन्द्र माथुर – रीढ़ की हड्डी
3. उदयशंकर भट्ट – दस हजार
4. विनोद रस्तोगी – बहू की विदा
5. उपेन्द्रनाथ अशक – नए मेहमान,
6. विष्णु प्रभाकर – सीमा रेखा
7. सेठ गोविन्ददास – सच्चा धर्म
8. जि.जे. हरिजीत – आखेट

III नुक्कड नाटक

1. गाँव से शहर तक
2. अपहारण भाईचारे का

2x12=24 Hr

Prescribed Books:

- 1) युगे-युगे क्रांति- विष्णु प्रभाकर, राजपाल और सन्स, दिल्ली
- 2) एकांकी संगम – गणपति भट्ट, डॉ. शिवराम, अमन प्रकाशन, कानपुर
- 3) नुक्कड नाटक- लोक भारती प्रकाशन, दिल्ली

First semester – Malayalam syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW06 K/ 21BAJ06 K	Kannada I
21BSW06 H/ 21BAJ06 H	Hindi I
21BSW06 M/ 21BAJ06 M	Malayalam I
21BSW06 O/ 21BAJ06 O	Online Mode I

Subject Code	21BSW06/ 21BAJ06	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

മലയാളം

ലക്ഷ്യങ്ങൾ

- മലയാള ഭാഷയിലെ കഥ, കവിത, നോവൽ, യാത്രവിവരണം, ജീവിച്ചരിത്രം തുടങ്ങിയ സാഹിത്യ ഗണങ്ങളെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള നല്ല ധാരണ കുട്ടികളിൽ വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക.
- സാമാന്യമായ സാഹിത്യ പരിചയവും വായനഭിരുചിയും ആസ്വാദനശേഷിയും വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക
- ഭാഷയുടെ അതിസാന്ദ്രരൂപമായ കവിതയിൽ ആസ്വാദനശേഷി വർദ്ധിപ്പിക്കുക

പഠന ഫലങ്ങൾ

- വിദ്യാർത്ഥികളിൽ വായനാ ശീലം വർദ്ധിക്കുന്നു
- സർഗ്ഗാത്മക രചനയിലെ സൗന്ദര്യത്മകത വർദ്ധിക്കുന്നു

- ഭാഷയുടെയും വിവിധ സംസ്കാരങ്ങളുടെയും വത്തെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള ധാരണ ലഭിക്കുന്നു

യൂണിറ്റ് 1 കവിതകൾ

പൂക്കാതിരിക്കാനെന്നിയ്ക്കാവതില്ലേ - അയ്യപ്പപ്പണിക്കർ
അങ്ങേ വീട്ടിലേക്ക് - ഇടശ്ശേരി
സന്ദർശനം - ബാലചന്ദ്രൻ ചുള്ളിക്കാട്
ഒരു പാട്ടു പിന്നെയും - സുഗതകുമാരി

യൂണിറ്റ് 2 ചെറുകഥകൾ

നെയ്പ്പായസം - മാധവിക്കുട്ടി
പ്ലാവില കഞ്ഞി - തകഴി

യൂണിറ്റ് 3 നോവൽ

ഉമ്മാച്ചു - ഉറുബ്
ബാല്യകാല സഖി - ബഷീർ

യൂണിറ്റ് 4 നാടകങ്ങൾ

നാടക ചരിത്രം
ഇന്ദിപ്പസ് - സി ജെ തോമസ്
സ്വപ്ന വാസവദത്തം - വള്ളത്തോൾ

യൂണിറ്റ് 5 ഭാഷ 5 വിചിന്തനം

ഭാഷയും സാഹിത്യവും - എ ശ്രീധര മേനോൻ
ഇംഗ്ലീഷിന്റെ സ്വാധീനം മലയാളത്തിൽ - ഡോ. ജാൻസി ജെയിംസ്

Second semester – Malayalam syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW16 K/ 21BAJ16 K	Kannada II
21BSW16 H/ 21BAJ16 H	Hindi II
21BSW16 M/ 21BAJ16 M	Malayalam II
21BSW16 O/ 21BAJ16 O	Online Mode II

Subject Code	21BSW16/ 21BAJ16	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

മലയാളം

ലക്ഷ്യങ്ങൾ

- മലയാള ഭാഷയിലെ കഥ, കവിത, നോവൽ, യാത്രവിവരണം, ജീവിച്ചരിത്രം തുടങ്ങിയ സാഹിത്യ ഗണങ്ങളെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള നല്ല ധാരണ കുട്ടികളിൽ വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക.
- സാമാന്യമായ സാഹിത്യ പരിചയവും വായനഭിരുചിയും ആസ്വാദനശേഷിയും വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക
- ഭാഷയുടെ അതിസാന്ദ്രപമായ കവിതയിൽ ആസ്വാദനശേഷി വർദ്ധിപ്പിക്കുക

പഠന ഫലങ്ങൾ

- വിദ്യാർത്ഥികളിൽ വായനാ ശീലം വർദ്ധിക്കുന്നു
- സർഗ്ഗാത്മക രചനയിലെ സൗന്ദര്യമകത വർദ്ധിക്കുന്നു
- ഭാഷയുടെയും വിവിധ സംസ്കാരങ്ങളുടെയും ഉത്ഭവത്തെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള ധാരണ ലഭിക്കുന്നു

യൂണിറ്റ് - 1 കവിതകൾ

- 1) മത്സ്യം - ടി. പി രാജീവൻ
- 2) വാഴക്കുല - ചങ്ങബുഴ
- 3) ചെറിയവ - കുമാരനാശാൻ
- 4) ഇനിയും മരിക്കാത്ത ഭൂമി - ഒ. എൻ. വി

യൂണിറ്റ് - 2 വിവർത്തനം

- 1) വിവർത്തനത്തിലേക്ക് ഒരു ജാലകം
- 2) വിവർത്തനം എന്ത്? എന്തിന്?
- 3) വിവർത്തനത്തിന്റെ പ്രശ്നങ്ങൾ

യൂണിറ്റ് - 3 ചെറുകഥ

- 1) മോതിരം - കാരൂർ
- 2) ഒട്ടകം - എസ്. കെ പൊറ്റക്കാട്
- 3) തിരുത്ത് - എൻ. എസ് മാധവൻ
- 4) പ്രഹരം - കെ. പി രാമുണ്ണി

യൂണിറ്റ് - 4 നാടകം

- 1) അടുക്കളയിൽ നിന്ന് അരങ്ങത്തേക്ക് - വി. ടി ഭദ്രത്തിരിപ്പാട്
- 2) രാവുണ്ണി - എം പി താജ്

യൂണിറ്റ് - 5 നോവൽ

- 1) ശബ്ദങ്ങൾ - ബഷീർ
- 2) കാലം - എം. ടി
- 3) നെല്ല് - വത്സല

Third semester – Malayalam syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW26 K/ 21BAJ26 K	Kannada III
21BSW26 H/ 21BAJ26 H	Hindi III
21BSW26 M/ 21BAJ26 M	Malayalam III
21BSW26 O/ 21BAJ26 O	Online Mode III

Subject Code	21BSW26/ 21BAJ26	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

മലയാളം

ലക്ഷ്യങ്ങൾ

- മലയാള ഭാഷയിലെ കഥ, കവിത, നോവൽ, യാത്രവിവരണം, ജീവിച്ചരിത്രം തുടങ്ങിയ സാഹിത്യ ഗണങ്ങളെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള നല്ല ധാരണ കുട്ടികളിൽ വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക.
- സാമാന്യമായ സാഹിത്യ പരിചയവും വായനഭിരുചിയും ആസ്വാദനശേഷിയും വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക
- ഭാഷയുടെ അതിസാന്ദ്രരൂപമായ കവിതയിൽ ആസ്വാദനശേഷി വർദ്ധിപ്പിക്കുക

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21BSW36 K/ 21BAJ36 K	Kannada IV
21BSW36 H/ 21BAJ36 H	Hindi IV
21BSW36 M/ 21BAJ36 M	Malayalam IV
21BSW36 O/ 21BAJ36 O	Online Mode IV

Subject Code	21BSW36/ 21BAJ36	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

മലയാളം

ലക്ഷ്യങ്ങൾ

- മലയാള ഭാഷയിലെ കഥ, കവിത, നോവൽ, യാത്രവിവരണം, ജീവിച്ചരിത്രം തുടങ്ങിയ സാഹിത്യ ഗണങ്ങളെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള നല്ല ധാരണ കുട്ടികളിൽ വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക.
- സാമാന്യമായ സാഹിത്യ പരിചയവും വായനഭിരുചിയും ആസ്വാദനശേഷിയും വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക
- ഭാഷയുടെ അതിസാന്ദ്രരൂപമായ കവിതയിൽ ആസ്വാദനശേഷി വർദ്ധിപ്പിക്കുക

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